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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATI

D2.6 Catalogue of OS career profiles and MVS - update

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Deliverable Abstract

This report updates Minimum Viable Skillsets (MVS) in Open Science, superseding the previously released *D2.1 Catalogue of Open Science Career Profiles – Minimum Viable Skillsets* by the Horizon Europe project Skills4EOSC. MVS aim to inform the design of learning objectives for training by assisting training designers to identify needs of their target groups. These Profiles describe ‘essential skills’ for roles that enable researchers, professionals, and stakeholders to practice Open Science (OS) with the support of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). In addition to updating the MVS structure, this report describes the efforts taken to learn from their application in training, and introduces new MVS, such as for Digital Collections Curator, and Scholarly Communication Specialist. The report recommends steps to sustain the MVS approach and resulting catalogue beyond the project.

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Glossary¹

CARE	Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, and Ethics
CSCCE	Centre for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement
DMP	Data Management Plan
ELSI	Ethical, Legal and Social Issues
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ETHRD IG	Education and Training on Handling of Research Data Interest Group (RDA)
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IT	Information Technology
JRC	Joint Research Centre
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
MVS	Minimum Viable Skillset
ORCC	Open Research Competencies Coalition
OS	Open Science
R&I	Research and Innovation
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RDM	Research Data Management
RI	Research Infrastructure
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
RSE	Research Software Engineer
T4fs	Terms for FAIR skills
WG	Working Group

¹ See also EOSC Glossary: EOSC Glossary Interest Group. (2020). EOSC Glossary (December 2020). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4472643>.

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Executive summary

This report updates Minimum Viable Skillsets (MVS) in Open Science, superseding the previously released *D2.1 Catalogue of Open Science Career Profiles – Minimum Viable Skillsets*. As well as updating the MVS structure, it describes the efforts taken to learn from their application in training, and introduces new MVS, such as for Digital Collections Curator, and Scholarly Communication Specialist. The report recommends steps to sustain the MVS approach and resulting catalogue beyond the project.

Section 2, **Skillsets in Open Science**, introduces the purpose of MVS and the MVS Catalogue. It considers the Open Science mission that motivates this work, and how that mission informs the Profile content and structure. This section also briefly describes each of the roles covered, and their organisational contexts.

Section 3, **How MVS Inform Training**, provides use cases for the Profiles, setting out when and how these add value to training design and other learning contexts. The MVS methodology is outlined as an approach to identifying high-level training objectives, as well as a first step to refining these through course design towards learning outcomes. The four main steps are described as follows:

1. Review the skills landscape to identify competence frameworks, policy documents, or other grey literature that identify expected skills for the role.
2. Use headings in the MVS template to review the literature in terms of skills essential for the role, based on background assumptions drawn from the literature about an appropriate mission for the role, its expected outcomes, and the main activities to be performed.
3. Map the essential skills to terms from relevant controlled vocabularies.
4. Validate the results based on feedback from training designers about the relevance of the MVS to their objectives for training people in the roles they are targeting, and with people in those roles.

Section 4, **Learning from Co-Creation**, identifies questions used both early in the process of developing the MVS, to obtain formative input to co-creation from trainers as direct users of the MVS, as well as final validation feedback from groups targeted by the relevant training. The section describes outcomes of the first round of (internal) feedback, describing an example of a learning path informed by it. The section also summarises changes made across the MVS.

Section 5, **Adoption to Adaptation: Competence Centres² and Research Performers**, describes what was learned from broader consultations within and beyond Skills4EOSC. The sources include the internal feedback from training tasks in Skills4EOSC, responses to a survey based on an online Review Questionnaire, and examples of MVS adoption in training by University of Tampere, and CSC Competence Centre. Notes of discussion in workshops held in the context of WP5: Open Science skills for Research Infrastructures and thematic communities and WP7: European Competence Centres and user support networks are also

² More information about the Skills4EOSC Competence Centre Network can be found on the website: <https://www.skills4eosc.eu/network>.

analysed to identify the opportunities and challenges for sustaining MVS beyond the Skills4EOSC project.

The concluding section 6, **Summary and Recommendations**, draws on the feedback gained from various sources, discusses prospects for adoption and adaptation of the MVS by Competence Centres and Research Performing Organisations, and makes recommendations for further work in the EOSC context. The main recommendation is that Competence Centres should adopt a co-creative methodology, which involves adapting the broad MVS to local contexts, organisations, and domains depending on their needs. The project aimed to cover a broad set of roles necessary for EOSC, without claiming that they cover all roles sufficient to meet all expectations. The recommendations include filling some notable gaps in the roles that MVS should be developed for, as well as adapting to context the MVS already provided by the project.

There are four appendices. **Appendix 1** provides an updated design model for the MVS catalogue, with definitions of its elements and their properties. **Appendix 2** shares internal project feedback received for an MVS profile. **Appendix 3** highlights feedback received from an external validation review questionnaire. Finally, **Appendix 4** offers some acknowledgements.

2. Skillsets in Open Science

2.1 Introducing Minimum Viable Skillsets

The notion of a 'minimum viable product' or MVP is well established in agile software development. A commonly used definition is given by the Agile Alliance:

"...that version of a new product that allows a team to collect the maximum amount of validated learning about customers with the least effort." ³

Skills4EOSC has adapted this concept to the 'Minimum Viable Skill set' (MVS).⁴ The 'Skill set' is a document profiling the range of skills a person needs to learn, or be trained in, to perform activities in a role that contributes to a desired outcome, i.e. towards Open Science (OS). The 'Minimum Viable' aspect refers to the purpose, which is to assist skills providers (trainers) to collect validated learning about the training required for a role and to develop courses that meet those requirements.⁵

To put this another way, an MVS can be used as a first step towards defining learning outcomes as input to the design of a more mature 'product.' Typically this will be a course or curriculum that defines such outcomes more specifically. We recommend that Competence Centres co-creating courses should be informed by feedback they gather from their target groups about the relevant MVS. The MVS in turn can then be refined based on experience in delivering courses and reused again in other contexts. A number of further use cases are outlined later in the report, together with the methodology.

In the Skills4EOSC context, an MVS describes essential skills and concepts required to deliver *Open Science* outcomes for communities and organisations, especially those using the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and providing services through it. Each MVS has been drafted from reference sources that define skills to practice OS e.g. competence frameworks and reports. The MVS are collected in a catalogue covering different OS roles. They include researchers, and various professional roles that support them, e.g. policy makers and other stakeholders.

The MVS is a key resource for the project's core objective of advancing OS skills, as the skillsets underpin a collection of modular learning pathways that span OS roles. Each MVS identifies the essential skills and competences in OS a particular role may need. An MVS is associated with a *profile* that gives additional context by stating assumptions about the OS mission and outcomes typically expected from the role, and the activities involved in contributing to those outcomes. While each MVS is role-specific, the roles are described at a broad level with the aim of accommodating alternative titles, for example for 'data professional' roles sharing a similar mission for OS.

³ <https://www.agilealliance.org/glossary/mvp/>

⁴ The report uses the terms 'MVS' throughout. The phrase 'MVS Profile' or simply 'Profile' is also used occasionally when the discussion focuses on the document content as a whole, rather than on the set of essential skills alone.

⁵ The term 'role' is used in the everyday sense of the contribution a person makes to fulfilling a desired outcome. A role does not equate to a person. A person may have several roles.

Skills4EOSC has identified 14 MVS skillsets, intended to span OS roles in various domains, organisational contexts, and at different career stages. These MVS are generic and do not cover an exhaustive list of roles. The recommendations in Section 5 strongly encourage localisation of skill sets and their extension to cover other roles.

2.2 Open Science in the EOSC context

Minimum Viable Skillsets (MVS) are intended to address gaps identified in the EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda. These include the lack of Open Science and data expertise and lack of a clear definition of data professional profiles and corresponding career paths. For Skills4EOSC, the main route to addressing these gaps is to first collate the MVS and then apply them alongside the 'FAIR by Design' methodology for designing learning resources that are aligned to the FAIR principles.⁶

There are many definitions of Open Science that may be used to provide an overall scope for the skillsets required. The League of European Research Universities (LERU, 2018), for example, highlight that "Open Science opens up new ways in which research/education/innovation are undertaken, archived and curated, and disseminated across the globe."⁷

Another definition of Open Science, particularly relevant to projects funded through the EC, is given in the *Programme Guide to Horizon Europe*, as follows:

*"Open science is a Research and Innovation (R&I) approach based on open cooperative work and systematic sharing of knowledge and tools as early and widely as possible in the process. It includes measures to ensure research outputs (such as publications, data, software, models, algorithms, and workflows) are reproducible and openly accessible according to domain standards. It includes participation in open peer-review; and measures to involve all relevant knowledge actors in co-creating R&I agendas and contents."*⁸

The UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science frames it similarly:

*"Open science is defined as an inclusive construct that combines various movements and practices aiming to make multilingual scientific knowledge openly available, accessible and reusable for everyone, to increase scientific collaborations and sharing of information for the benefits of science and society, and to open the processes of scientific knowledge creation, evaluation and communication to societal actors beyond the traditional scientific community. It comprises all scientific disciplines and aspects of scholarly practices, including basic and applied sciences, natural and social sciences and the humanities, and it builds on the following key pillars: open scientific knowledge, open science infrastructures, science communication, open engagement of societal actors and open dialogue with other knowledge systems."*⁹

⁶ Filiposka, Sonja, et al. (2023). D2.2 Methodology for FAIR-by-Design Learning Materials (1.4). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8305540>.

⁷ LERU (2018) Ayris, Paul et al. 'Open Science and its role in universities: a roadmap for cultural change'. Advice Paper. <https://www.leru.org/publications/open-science-and-its-role-in-universities-a-roadmap-for-cultural-change>

⁸ European Commission (2023) Horizon Europe Programme Guide v3.0 April 2023 (pp.41-42) https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/programme-guide_horizon_en.pdf

⁹ UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science (2021) Paris. UNESCO ([p.7](#))

These definitions of Open Science offer a starting point for defining MVS, although in our view it is not desirable to be constrained by any specific definition. What is important is that some form of general statement of requirements is used and, ideally, that it should identify the kinds of actors involved, the mission and outcomes expected of them, and the activities they are expected to perform to realise benefits of Open Science.

The University of Cape Town (UCT) produced a graphic shown in Figure 1 to illustrate benefits associated with the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science.

Figure 1 Why Open Science? Source University of Cape Town (CC-BY-SA 4.0) ¹⁰

2.3 Contents of an MVS

The Skills4EOSC template for an MVS¹¹ consists of a short document (e.g. 4-6 pp.). Its structure is informed by the scope outlined in the previous section, while its content for any particular role is drawn from a landscape analysis of literature about the relevant skills. This should focus on articles and reports that identify roles and skills needed for Open Science. The focus of current MVS is mainly on researchers and data-related professional roles found in Research Performing Organisations (RPOs) and Research Infrastructures (RI), plus other roles on the interface between science and society, including policy makers.

To assist in the literature search for relevant skills and competences, five high-level dimensions of Open Science based on the Horizon Europe guidance were used.¹² These are

<https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000379949.locale=en>

¹⁰ https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:UCT_RDM_Why-Open-Science.png

¹¹ Whyte, A., et al. (2024). Template for a Minimum Viable Skillset (1.1). Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10977747>.

¹² European Commission (2023) Horizon Europe Programme Guide v3.0 April 2023 (pp. 40-48)

https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/programmeguide_horizon_en.pdf

shown in Figure 2. The MVS draws on these high-level dimensions to identify relevant content for the main sections of the document. Focusing on a specific role, the MVS summarises an overall OS mission for that role, together with the outcomes and activities typically expected of the role, as far as these relate to OS.

Figure 2. High Level Dimensions of Open Science

Based on the information about these dimensions drawn from literature sources, each Profile describes the elements listed below:

- **Essential skills:** bullet point shortlists of relevant competences. These include both:
 - **Specialist** skills: specific to a scientific or professional domain, or to the organisational context in which these skills are applied.
 - **Transversal** or 'soft' skills: are not specific to the domain or organisational context.
- **Background assumptions**
 - **Mission:** what this role does in relation to Open Science, both broadly defined and within the EOSC context.
 - **Outcomes:** further statements describing results that should be achieved through practising OS.
 - **Activities:** actions performed to accomplish the outcomes.

2.4 Sources for MVS Roles and Skills Landscape Analysis

A key source for identifying roles to profile was the framework provided by the 2021 report of the EOSC Working Group on Skills and Training.¹³ This mapped well to the following roles for which Skills4EOSC partners expected to deliver courses and curricula:

- Data stewards and 'data professionals' more broadly
- Researchers, including PhD students
- Policymakers and knowledge brokers or 'honest brokers' in the science-society interface
- Research Infrastructure professionals

This initial list of 'data professional' roles was expanded, informed by a survey and literature review conducted by the RDA Professionalising Data Stewardship Interest Group.¹⁴ The list was refined further through co-creation surveys carried out among project partners and public responses. The final selection of roles is illustrated in Figure 4. As shown, the selection spans different organisational contexts, domains, and career stages.¹⁵

Figure 4 Roles selected for Minimum Viable Skillset Profiles

¹³ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (2021) Manola, N., Lazzeri, E., Barker, M. et al., *Digital skills for FAIR and Open Science – Report from the EOSC Executive Board Skills and Training Working Group*, Manola, N.(editor), Lazzeri, E.(editor), Barker, M.(editor), Kuchma, I.(editor), Gaillard, V.(editor), Stoy, L.(editor), Publications Office, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/59065> (Figure 3. P.17)

¹⁴ Wildgaard, L., & Rantasaari, J. (2022). RDA Professionalising Data Stewardship - Data Stewardship Landscape Report Resource Matrix [Data set]. Research Data Alliance. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00077>

¹⁵ Colours in the figure are for illustration only.

Profiles were compiled collaboratively, working in sub-groups dedicated to specific roles. A collection of literature sources was compiled based on those used in writing the MVS. The sources are available in a [Zotero group collection](#)¹⁶ (Note that access requires a Zotero account). The sources collected include reports, peer-reviewed journal articles, and deliverables from other EC-funded projects. The sources of Open Science training requirements also include policies of research funders or the relevant government agencies. The geographic scope of these sources varied, with a bias towards those originating from Member States that have policies advocating that RPOs establish data professional roles, including The Netherlands, Denmark, France, and the United Kingdom.

2.5 Filling Gaps between Policy and Learning Outcomes

We propose that MVS provide value by filling a gap between policies that advocate capacity building for certain roles to support Open Science implementation and the learning outcomes that trainers are expected to translate such policies into.

At a general level, trainers can already easily identify learning outcomes for Open Science which they can fit to their training objectives. They can refer to introductory courses from a variety of providers e.g. OpenAIRE, Eurodoc, as well as Skills4EOSC. Such sources may well be useful as an introduction to core principles, practices, and benefits, at a general level similar to that of the UNESCO Recommendation and Horizon Europe policy guidance already mentioned in this section. Trainers can also use generative AI tools to generate learning objectives for Open Science, and tailor their prompt to specific roles. However, Open Science training requirements that stem from policies of research funders or relevant government agencies may place obligations on Research Performing Organisations to fulfil specific functions. These typically include expectations that Research Performers will establish processes for managing research data according to FAIR Principles, or that they will govern the ethical handling of research data according to related principles of Responsible Research and Innovation.

At the more specialised level, various roles have well-known competence frameworks that provide detailed statements of skills, knowledge or aptitudes required. Examples include the EDISON framework for Data Scientists¹⁷ and the DPC Digital Preservation Competency Framework.¹⁸

Accordingly, MVS may fill a gap for trainers where the roles involved in meeting funder and organisational expectations have no competence framework, or none that mention Open Science. Also where competence frameworks do exist, these are generally relatively complex documents. The MVS offer a simple approach to filling the gap between policy and training practice in an easy to read document. Each MVS matches the selected 'essential skills' to terms sourced from relevant controlled vocabularies or terminologies, which have similar

¹⁶ Note that this linked group collection is a different link listed in the first iteration of this Catalogue. It has since been updated to be a public, open library.

¹⁷ <https://edison-project.eu/data-science-competence-framework-cf-ds/>

¹⁸ <https://www.dpconline.org/digipres/prof-development/dp-competency>

levels of granularity to learning outcomes and can thus stimulate discussion of how to operationalise learning outcomes in training design.

The MVS are tagged using relevant terminologies that range from simple glossaries to machine-readable ontologies. In the former, the CSCCE glossary and 'skills wheel' for science community manager is included mainly for 'soft skills' covering interpersonal and communication aspects of Open Science.¹⁹ For research roles, the ResearchComp framework²⁰ is also applied.

Two highly relevant ontologies are also used as a source of Open Science Skills Terms. These are:

- terms4FAIRskills (t4fs) ontology,²¹ which provides terms oriented to technology, domain, and project management aspects of FAIR data stewardship.
- ESCO, the European Skills, Competences, Qualifications, and Occupations ontology, in particular the 'pillars' which relate to transversal skills and competences, and to research skills.²²

ESCO, in particular, has been a focus of the MVS since publication of the initial version in Skills4EOSC D2.1.²³ Adopting machine-readable terms from the ontologies is also helpful towards making the MVS available as FAIR digital objects, e.g. by providing metadata terms to be applied according to the FAIR by Design methodology.²⁴

2.6 Catalogue Metadata and Platform Sources

Minimum Viable Skillsets (MVS) are strongly related to learning resources on purpose. As such, it is recommended that MVS are catalogued with appropriate metadata to make them FAIR. Sources of metadata to make learning resources FAIR are reviewed in the Skills4EOSC FAIR by Design Methodology, and for this purpose, the minimal metadata for learning resources identified by the RDA Interest Group on Education and Training in Handling Research Data (ETHRD-IG) was selected.²⁵

The RDA ETHRD-IG metadata comprises the set of recommended elements in Table 2, which defines how they are applied to the MVS.

¹⁹ CSCCE Glossary of Skills Wheel terms: <https://www.cscce.org/resources/glossary/>

²⁰ ResearchComp: The European Competence Framework for Researchers: https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/jobs-research/researchcomp-european-competence-framework-researchers_en

²¹ terms4FAIRskills (tf4s) <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols4/ontologies/t4fs>

²² ESCO Classification: <https://esco.ec.europa.eu/en/classification>

²³ Whyte, A., Green, D., Avanço, K., Di Giorgio, S., Gingold, A., Horton, L., Koteska, B., Kyprianou, K., Prnjat, O., Rauste, P., Schirru, L., Sowinski, C., Torres Ramos, G., van Leersum, N., Sharma, C., Méndez, E., & Lazzeri, E. (2023). *D2.1 Catalogue of Open Science Career Profiles - Minimum Viable Skillsets (v1.2)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8101903>

²⁴ Filiposka, Sonja, et al. (2023). D2.2 Methodology for FAIR-by-Design Learning Materials (1.4). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8305540>.

²⁵ Hoebelheinrich, N. J., et al. (2022). Recommendations for a minimal metadata set to aid harmonised discovery of learning resources (Version 1.0). Research Data Alliance. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00073>.

Element Name	RDA ETHRD-IG Definition	Application to MVS
Title	The human readable name of the resource.	MVS title e.g. 'Minimum Viable Skillset for Data Stewards'
Abstract / Description	A brief synopsis about or description of the learning resource.	Introduction to the MVS
Author(s)	Name of entity(ies) authoring the resource.	Authors contributing to the MVS
Primary Language	Language in which the resource was originally published or made available.	Language the MVS is published in.
Keyword(s)	Keywords or tags used to describe the resource.	Open Science Skills Terms, selected e.g. from ESCO
License	A license document that applies to this content, typically indicated by URL	CC-BY-4.0
Version Date	Version date for the most recently published or broadcast resource.	Version date of the MVS
URL to Resource	URL that resolves to the learning resource or to a "landing page" for the resource that contains important contextual information including the direct resolvable link to the resource, if applicable.	DOI link in MVS Catalogue (Zenodo collection)
Resource URL Type	Designation of the identifier scheme used for the resource URL, e.g., DOI, ARK, Handle.	DOI
Target Group (Audience)	Principal users(s) for which the resource was designed.	Trainers and educators
Learning Resource Type	The predominant type or kind that characterizes the learning resource.	Curricular resource
Learning Outcome	Description of knowledge, skills or abilities a learner should acquire.	Knowledge of key topics to cover in developing the competences of a role involved in performing or supporting Open Science
Access Cost	Access cost: Choice stating whether or not there is a fee for use of the resource (CV = Y/N/Maybe	N
Expertise (Skill) Level	Target skill level in the topic being taught; example values include: beginner, intermediate, advanced.	Beginner

Table 2 Catalogue metadata for MVS

The catalogue of all currently available MVS is available in two forms that each apply the above where feasible:

- Zenodo record providing an Annex to the present report, in PDF form.²⁶

²⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15761916>

- Github repository providing the MVSs in markdown text format.²⁷

2.7 Brief Outline of Roles Profiled

The scope of the 14 MVS listed in the catalogue is outlined below. It is recognised that role titles here can be used with other associated function titles. For instance, for roles attributed to 'Data Steward,' similar titles such as Data Librarian and Research Data Management Specialists are quite often used and their roles are similar. The role titles and categories used align with Skills4EOSC course development tasks and are not prescriptive. Competence centres, trainers, and other stakeholders are able to modify an MVS to fit their specific context, including role titles. For convenience, the roles are grouped as follows:

- Data professionals: data steward, digital collections curator.
- Research professionals: researcher (early career, senior), research infrastructure professional, scholarly communications professional, ethics advisor, legal expert.
- Research users: student (undergraduate, masters), civil servant, knowledge broker, policymaker (research policy, evidence-based policy).

2.7.1 Data Professionals

DATA STEWARD: Works with stakeholders to establish, govern and maintain processes to collect research data, make it usable for research objectives, facilitate its transformation into research output, assist in quality assurance, and support informed decision-making on its openness for reuse according to ethical, legal, and social expectations. The Profile includes two variations - 'Coordinator' and 'Embedded' roles. These represent two ends of a centralisation spectrum that is highly variable between Research Performing Organisations. '**Coordinator**' describes a role providing support across an organisation's research domains and units. At the other end of the spectrum, '**Embedded**' describes a role close to a research team and to its domain-specific practices.

DIGITAL COLLECTIONS CURATOR: Supports digitisation and works with others to ensure the long-term preservation and reusability of data derived from collections. Working in the Library, Archive, or Museum context, they advise and train researchers and other staff on policy, guidelines, data management plans, and infrastructure. They also apply tools to manage data for collections and research domains relevant to the institution.

2.7.2 Research Professionals

RESEARCHER - EARLY CAREER: Ensures that the benefits which openness brings, such as the accessibility, reproducibility, and transparency of research, are available to students, colleagues, and to society as a whole. The early career researcher (ECR) facilitates Open Science via data sharing, exploring and reusing data, data publication, making code available, promoting open research through peer review, and reproducible research.

RESEARCHER - SENIOR: Acts as a catalyst for change, showing leadership through implementing Open Science policies in their own research projects and teams, also in mentoring and training students, raising awareness of open science among Undergraduate

²⁷ <https://fair-by-design-methodology.github.io/MVS/latest/>

and Master's Students, and acting as a bridge between the scientific community and technical services.

RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE PROFESSIONAL: Works for a Research Infrastructure supporting research communities to conduct Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), and Open Science. May be responsible for providing, handling and maintaining services, resources, training, and tools; supporting, monitoring and improving a common space for sharing best practices in FAIR and Open Science.

SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATIONS PROFESSIONAL: Deals with artifacts such as articles, books, posts, annotations. They engage with Open Science by ensuring open access to these artifacts, and more broadly their full integration into the OS environment. Scholarly Communications Professionals apply OS and RDM principles to traditional and innovative forms of artifacts, and address aspects of Open Science beyond Research Data Management.

ETHICS ADVISOR: Provides guidance on a range of ethical issues, including research involving AI systems, dual-use technologies, animal experimentation, and broader societal impacts. They help anticipate and address potential ethical dilemmas thereby ensuring that research activities respect fundamental values such as accountability, transparency, inclusivity, and respect for diversity.

LEGAL EXPERT: Ensures compliance with regulations, such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), while also facilitating open access to research materials, data reuse, and collaboration. Legal experts also assist in aligning organisations with legal standards, mitigating risks related to privacy, intellectual property, and contractual obligations.

2.7.3 Research users

STUDENT – MASTERS LEVEL: Applies skills and competencies in Open Science (OS) in the context of Master's level education, by incorporating open methods into their project workflows for a focused study.

STUDENT – UNDERGRADUATE LEVEL: Acquires data literacy and knowledge of the FAIR principles, as a basis for any Open Science activities and knowledge relevant to their career.

CIVIL SERVANT: Promotes transparency and accountability in the context of Open Science, by facilitating the appropriate access to and re-use of scientific data for public benefit. They ensure that administrative processes are neutral, non-partisan, and aligned with ethical standards.

KNOWLEDGE BROKER: Responsible for facilitating the dissemination of scientific information, ensuring that research findings are accessible and actionable for various audiences. Knowledge brokers promote transparency and collaboration, particularly in the context of Open Science, by bridging the gap between research and practice, enabling informed decision-making.

POLICYMAKER FOR RESEARCH: Facilitates the development and promotion of Open Science policies. They create frameworks and provide the necessary support to promote the adoption of OS practices at national and international levels. This includes mobilising resources, building partnerships, and ensuring policies align with OS principles like FAIR.

POLICYMAKER – EVIDENCE-BASED POLICY: Gathers, assesses, and synthesises credible research data to design policies addressing specific societal or scientific issues. They ensure that policy decisions are data-driven and aligned with the principles of Open Science, considering the relevance and quality of evidence to inform their decisions.

2.8 MVS and Career Paths

The MVS recognise various stages an individual researcher or data professional may take throughout their career. These are represented through the following stages:

- 1) **Student:** an undergraduate or graduate student undertaking a taught degree course at a recognised higher education institution.
- 2) **Research Actor:** performs research as a PhD student or postdoctoral researcher, or supports the research process undertaken by others, e.g. by providing services, making policy for research, or making policies that are informed by research results.
- 3) **Senior Research Actor:** has responsibilities for supervising research or practitioners who support research, or for leading implementation of Open Science within and across organisations.

These are informed by the European Framework for Research Careers, which defines four career levels (R1-R4). The absence of similarly well-defined career paths for data professionals is one of the challenges Skills4EOSC aims to address. By coupling generic Minimum Viable Skillsets to modular learning pathways that span OS roles, and offering a framework for applying digital credentials, Skills4EOSC has made progress towards enabling individuals to build careers with enough flexibility to work around current institutional limitations and also gain recognition.

3. How MVS Support Skills Development

3.1 Use cases for Minimum Viable Skillsets

The main use case for MVS is for trainers to learn about which skills they will need to develop in their learners for the Open Science role(s) their training is to target. The MVS is intended to be an evolving “plan”, rather than a final product. The MVS does this by encapsulating what a person needs to learn, or be trained in, to be able to perform their role and contribute to the desired outcomes for Open Science.

The MVS summarises ‘essential skills’, mapping these to standard terms for skills and competences. By also making explicit the trainers’ assumptions about the learners’ context, an MVS may be used to help the providers of skills and training to collect validated learning about training needs for the role, and develop courses that meet those needs. The authors see the MVS as a resource for an ongoing conversation that trainers need to have about learning objectives for Open Science with other trainers, with people in the roles they are targeting, and with other stakeholders, such as policymakers and leaders at their organisations.

The profiles will also be helpful in the following contexts:

- **Individual researchers and data professionals** aiming to proactively develop their skills can refer to the MVS for suggested competences. The MVS may also be useful to refer to in the context of their organisation’s career development process.
- **Team leaders** of researchers and data professionals aiming to build capacity in Open Science by improving skills of existing staff or recruiting people to new roles. The MVS offers a simple format for self-assessing and comparing competences across roles relevant in their context, and finding opportunities to fill them within the organisation.
- **Professional networks** aiming to build the competences of any of the relevant professional roles, and **Competence Centres** aiming to develop their capabilities as centres of expertise in Open Science. In this case, the MVS may help to identify any competence gaps networks and Competence Centres may want to target.
- **Legal and Ethics experts** aiming to identify where legal and ethical experts can contribute their expertise in other roles, such as Data Stewards, and identify areas where training and coordination is needed. These roles also have their own MVS.
- **Policymakers, Civil Servants, and Knowledge Brokers** aiming to define what competence areas to prioritise and define areas in need of capacity building. These roles also have their own MVS.

3.2 Methodology to Co-create a MVS

An MVS may be used either independently or as an integral part of the FAIR-by-design methodology in designing training materials. In the case of a course being designed using the FAIR-by-design approach, the course authors would use or co-create an MVS in the first three phases, from Prepare to Discover and Design, as Figure 5 illustrates.²⁸

²⁸ A micro-learning package about the FAIR-by-design methodology is available here: <https://fair-by-design-methodology.github.io/microlearning/latest/03%20Design/design/>.

Figure 5. MVS role in FAIR-by-Design methodology

MVS co-creation is a collaborative authoring and review process outlined in Figure 6 and described below.

Figure 6. MVS co-creation steps

The MVS co-creation process involves six steps, which may need to be repeated through successive drafts. First, drafting the MVS Profile document involves the three steps shown on the left side of Figure 6: defining the use case(s), describing the role, OS mission and

outcomes, and identifying essential skills and selecting ontology terms. The other three steps involve using the MVS to inform learning outcomes, reviewing the essential skills listed in the MVS based on that experience, and seeking feedback from others (trainers, target groups, broader stakeholders) on how well it fulfils the use case, and meets expectations.

In Skills4EOSC, successive drafts of each MVS were reviewed and critiqued, with each iteration broadening the range of actors whose comments were sought.

- The first target group were intended users of the MVS, in each case a different group of course and curriculum developers within Skills4EOSC Work Packages.
- The next targets were selected as 'critical friends' among the stakeholders we anticipated would be interested in contributing. These were selected on the basis that they had both a publicly stated interest in developing skills for the relevant role, e.g. relevant RDA groups and relevant national or international online communities for data professionals.

Based on this experience and the larger co-creation methodology developed and implemented within the project, we would recommend to repeat steps. This allows for continuous adjustment of the MVS so that suited for the target audience. For example, the 'Review MVS against use case' step may be used to benefit from community feedback in advance of a training pilot, and then repeat it after trainers have reflected on that pilot.

All six steps can involve trainers, individuals in the target groups (roles), and other stakeholders in the training outcome. The specific mix is likely to depend on the novelty of the role in the organisation concerned. Newer roles are likely to require broader involvement to achieve a consensus. The people and resources available for the training or other skills development project will certainly influence the nature and extent of collaboration.

3.2.1 Define use case(s)

The use cases will vary according to the role(s) the MVS are to be developed for, and the intended users of the MVS e.g., trainers or managers of the roles. In the case of training design, the authors of the MVS will ideally be the same individuals as those designing the course materials. In drafting the content of the MVS, the authors will benefit from consulting relevant people in the target role described in the MVS (or people they work with).

3.2.2 Describe the role, OS mission, and outcomes

The next step is to describe the role, and the expected OS mission, outcomes, and activities those outcomes depend on (the same ones that the organisation aims to improve skills in). This may benefit from analysis of relevant literature, e.g. documents from EOSC, national OS strategies and policy statements, or guidance from Research Infrastructures, Competence Centres and relevant professional networks.

In Skills4EOSC, the first round of drafting referred to the Open Science definitions and 'dimensions' based on Horizon Europe guidance, discussed in section 2. Then the MVS template headings were used as a minimal classification scheme for analysing literature sources.

The resulting Skills4EOSC bibliography²⁹ is available for reuse and includes competence frameworks, reports on skill requirements and related literature. For other roles, it may also be helpful to collect and review job descriptions, e. g. if there is insufficient recent literature available to describe skills requirements for the role in question.³⁰

Feedback on a draft MVS at this stage could also be sought from colleagues whose role overlaps with the target role to accomplish the same OS outcomes.

3.2.3 Identify essential skills and select OS taxonomy terms

The next step is to discuss and agree on the description of essential skills, and then select OS taxonomy terms from the recommended sources. This is a straightforward process involving the following:

1. Identify which statements the terms are to be applied to. This should be the 'essential skills and competences' in the MVS. Optionally, the 'activities' these relate to can be included, particularly if they may clarify which terms apply.
2. For each statement, select from the list of terms for each source (CSCCE Glossary, ResearchComp, t4FS, ESCO). To mitigate the risk of subjective bias in selecting the terms, it is recommended that three (3) or more people decide on them through consensus. The consensus process involves several people selecting terms independently and a further person adjudicating discussions.
3. Compile a table listing the terms selected, copy these terms to the MVS, and include the links to the definitions given in the terminology sources (t4FS, or CSCCE Glossary).
4. Review the selected terms against the MVS 'essential skills and competences' statements to consider rewording these, e.g. to make learning outcomes more explicit.

3.2.4 Use MVS to inform learning outcomes

This corresponds to the *Discover* and *Design* phases of the FAIR-by-design methodology outlined in Figure 5. These phases are supported by either creating a new MVS or reusing and adapting an existing one. Suggested applications of the MVS include:

- The MVS lists activities the role is expected to perform. These activities and the terminology used to describe them can inform learning objectives and learning outcomes. (Prepare and Design phases)
- The MVS content, especially the 'Essential skills' and listed 'Open Science skills terms' may be used as search terms to identify existing resources that could be relevant to include in the training material. (Discover phase)
- The MVS lists references to further reading which may include learning resources for course designers and disciplinary specific as well as disciplinary agnostic information about the role. (Discover phase)
- The MVS describes skills that for each role that can be used to inform expectations and prerequisites. (Design phase)

²⁹ Available in an open Zotero group collection, https://www.zotero.org/groups/6024496/t2.1_skills4eoscmvs_landscaping-2025/library.

³⁰ A similar approach was undertaken during the FAIRsFAIR project (2019-2022). <https://www.fairsfair.eu/fair-frameworks-training-programmes>.

- The MVS content may be used to design training materials that can be put into a training programme, supporting career advancement and continuous learning. (Design phase)

3.2.5 Review essential skills based on experience

Skills4EOSC tested the relevance of the MVS 'essential skills' in training design by developing courses based on the first set of MVS published in 2023. After the development and facilitation of these courses, the training leads and designers were asked a set of questions in relation to its use in creating course materials. The questions were as follows:

1. What learning objectives were defined for this learning path?
2. Which of the following statements best describes how the MVS was used when the learning objectives were defined?
 - a) Learning objectives were defined without referring to the MVS.
 - b) The MVS indirectly influenced the learning objectives by providing background information on skills that are considered essential to the role.
 - c) Were substantially based on the MVS, e.g. used similar wording.
3. Which aspects of the MVS were most and least useful for designing the learning path?
4. What lessons should the MVS authors learn, based on your experience of using the MVS?
5. How well do the proposed 'key Open Science skills terms' represent the essential skills for the respective MVS?
6. Are you aware of any organisations, projects, or other initiatives interested in using the MVS for their skills development?

3.2.6 Review MVS against use case

The Skills4EOSC methodology does not limit the approaches used to review how well the MVS meet their defined use case, as the appropriate method will depend on that use case and the organisation concerned. In the project, a 'Review Questionnaire' was designed to facilitate the feedback, in the interest of opening this to as wide an audience as possible. Other approaches are feasible, e.g. workshop discussions or focus groups.

Requests for feedback and external validation of the MVS against its primary use case (training design) were targeted at relevant networks, including but not limited to the following:

- Skills4EOSC Competence Centre network
- Participants in the Skills4EOSC WP5 workshop for Professional networks
- Network for Education and Research Quality (NERQ) and Open Science Learning GATE.
- Subscribers to the UK Research Data Management mailing list ('research-dataman')

The questionnaire was built with the EU Survey tool,³¹ and focused on two main purposes:

- To check if the proposed Minimum Viable Skills profiles target the 'essential' learning outcomes appropriately for various roles.
- To establish whether or not respondents considered the MVS adaptable to their organisation and to the communities they target in their training.

³¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/>

The questionnaire offers a short introduction to the MVS purpose and scope, based on Section 2 of this report. It then lists the roles covered and invites respondents to select one that best fits their own, before selecting which role they would like to review.

The questionnaire respondents were first asked to provide “a few short phrases to express what you believe are the main skills that a person in this role needs to work effectively within Open Science.” They were then invited to look at the MVS essential skills and suggest if any of those listed should be changed.

Two closed single-choice questions were used:

In your view, how well do the skills listed above match skills this role requires to practice Open Science? (7 point rating scale)

How useful would you expect the above profile to be for identifying the training needs of your own organisation? (selection of one from the following options)

- I expect this MVS
 - Can be used easily without changing much of the text or format.
 - Can be used by making substantial changes to the text or the format
 - Would only be used with completely different text or format
 - Would be irrelevant in our context
- I cannot answer

A further open question invited respondents to provide any other feedback they wanted, and to identify themselves if they wished to be acknowledged, but were anonymous by default. Section 4 summarises the feedback received.

4. Outcomes from Co-creation

4.1 First Iteration: Steps to Co-create the MVS Catalogue

Co-creation is a key theme of Skills4EOSC and, as a result, the project partners undertook extensive outreach activities to involve the wider community of interest in EOSC skills development. This section gives an account of how the process outlined in section 3 was applied, to consult people inside and outside the project about the MVS design and content.

To kickstart the process, internal meetings were held with various work packages, particularly WP3, focused on "OS training for evidence-based policy and public administration." These meetings aimed to define and discuss the Minimum Viable Skillset (MVS) for Policymakers and share the approach taken. Additionally, continuous consultation with the Ethical, Legal, and Social Issues (ELSI) WP ensured the inclusion of ELSI skills for each profile, leading to the creation of separate profiles for legal experts and data ethicists/ethics advisors.

Having consolidated a first draft of the Open Science Career Profiles and MVS, which was released and published on Zenodo at the end of February 2023,³² Skills4EOSC launched a community review of the first draft of this report.³³ The draft provided a definition and template for the MVS, along with an initial example for policymakers. Feedback on the MVS approach, examples, and priorities for further profiles was collected in March 2023 through a questionnaire on EU Survey.³⁴

Responses were directly invited from various organisations and channels, including EOSC Forum, the EOSC Task Forces³⁵ 'Upskilling Countries to engage in EOSC', 'Data Stewardship Curricula and Career Paths,' and 'The Research careers, recognition and credit'. Also consulted were the Community of Practice for Training Coordinators (CoP),³⁶ RDA ETHRD IG focus group³⁷, JRC community of trainers³⁸, Open Research Competencies Coalition (ORCC), and FAIR-IMPACT coordinator. These engagements aimed to gather valuable insights and perspectives from a well-informed experts.

The consultation process had a limited response of 11 contributions. While few in number, they played a significant role in determining the prioritisation of roles to characterise, as follows:-

- Very high priority: Data Steward/Curator, Researcher, RI Manager
- High priority: Policymaker (for Open Science, and Research-informed policy areas), Principal Investigator (Senior Researcher), Lab Coordinator, Data Manager, RDM Coordinator, Scholarly Communications Professional, Research Software Engineer, Data Scientist, Data Analyst, Data Engineer, User Support Professional, Research Manager
- Moderate priority: Knowledge Broker, Civil Servant

³² <https://zenodo.org/record/7686263#.ZGZE73ZByUk>

³³ See the section in the project's web site: <https://www.skills4eosc.eu/participate/materials-for-community-review>

³⁴ <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/b5b03d28-733c-b791-5852-2435c0f02623>

³⁵ <https://eosc.eu/eosc-task-forces>

³⁶ <https://www.openaire.eu/cop-training>

³⁷ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/group/education-and-training-handling-research-data-ig/post/rda-ethrd-ig-focus-group-training>

³⁸ https://knowledge4policy.ec.europa.eu/home_en

The first release of the catalogue (D2.1) included all of the above roles, with some exceptions. These included roles that we judged similar enough to list as synonyms of those already covered, i.e. Lab Coordinator (RI Manager), Data Manager and RDM Coordinator (both covered by Data Steward MVS).

In other cases, roles were not addressed because the authors were aware that role profiles were either well covered already, or would be likely covered through related work elsewhere. These included Data Scientist, Data Analyst, and Data Engineer, roles already described through the EDISON project and national initiatives such as the UK's Turing Institute.

To focus the limited resources available for developing further MVS, two roles were selected on the basis that they were distinct enough to warrant separate profiles. These were the Scholarly Communications Professional, and the Digital Collections Curator.

4.2 Second Iteration: Additions to the MVS Catalogue

4.2.1 Scholarly Communications Professional

The traditional focus of Research Data Management (RDM) on research datasets tends to obscure the importance of scholarly communication contents in Open Science. Scholarly communication outputs (articles, books, blog posts, etc.) are not only a complement to research taking the form of publications, but may also be considered research data. As such they can be used as primary data for research, applying best practices very similar to the ones used in the management of research data. Scholarly communication skills and practices involved in treating outputs as data for reuse were therefore synthesised in a dedicated MVS.

The first step in building the Scholarly Communications Professional MVS was to define its scope more clearly. This was done first by listing the main official job positions and second by identifying the type of organisations such professionals most often work for. Using OPERAS RI, a project partner and a research infrastructure representing a large community of open scholarly communication actors as an example, it was decided to consider a broad scope of these professionals working in a variety of contexts. Therefore, the MVS profile simultaneously considered publishers, editors, librarians, and, more generally, operators of services and infrastructures supporting open scholarly communication (e.g. publishing platforms, university publishing services).

The main challenge in building the MVS was the lack of dedicated documentation of competences for relevant activities. There were no references either covering the scholarly communications job positions as a whole, or specifically the data management skills of an editor or a publishing service operator. Therefore, the creation process of the MVS started essentially from the rather extensive documentation about librarians and data librarians, particularly documentation provided by LIBER,³⁹ which was then expanded based on the experience of the task members, who were themselves scholarly communication

³⁹ McCaffrey, C., Meyer, T., Riera Quintero, C., Swiatek, C., Marcerou-Ramel, N., Gillén, C., Clavel, K., Wojciechowska, A., Brinken, H., Prevoo, M., & Egerton, F. (2020). Open Science Skills Visualisation - Visualisation des compétences en science ouverte (Version 2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4727592>

professionals and well engaged with their community. The first drafting of the MVS thus relied on a mix of documentation, personal experience, and community feedback, conforming to the objective of a co-creation process.

The first draft of the MVS was presented to one component of OPERAS RI: the OpenEdition French RI, a publishing platform dedicated to Social Sciences and Humanities journals, books and blogs. The OpenEdition team, precisely composed of Scholarly Communication Professionals, made suggestions that helped prepare the MVS for its internal review by the task members. This revised version was then presented to Skills4EOSC partners in WP4, specifically in T4.2, where an MVS specifically for data librarians was being considered.⁴⁰ After this presentation, WP4 members provided their feedback about the Scholarly Communication professional MVS, aiding in further refinement. The final version of this MVS incorporates this internal and external feedback, thus achieving a fruitful co-creation process.

4.2.2 Digital Collections Curator

An MVS for Digital Collections Curators was developed as part of the process of creating a Skills4EOSC train-the-trainer course for this community. The Data Steward MVS was used as a starting point for the new MVS, as the Digital Collection Curator role was seen as having similar skills requirements as that role but with a focus on research digital objects that are derived from collections along with datasets derived from these digital objects. The derived MVS was adapted based on insights on the role of Digital Collections Curator gathered through a workshop with the Austrian GLAM (galleries, libraries, archives, museums) community in Vienna in April 2024 and additional desk research. A total of 91 individuals from 35 different institutions across the GLAM and related sectors took part in the workshop.

The draft MVS was developed iteratively by the task group, and annotated using terms selected from a subset of the ESCO ontology. The resulting MVS was shared with members of the RDA Collections as Data Interest Group⁴¹ for comment, initiating contributions from members of this group in the subsequent pilot of the train-the-trainer course.

4.3 Feedback from Training Pilots

Feedback on the MVS was provided from two sources: within the project partners using MVS to inform design of their training courses, and then more widely from respondents to an MVS Review questionnaire. This section covers the former. The examples that follow illustrate three ways that the MVS connected with training tasks in the project, demonstrating increasing impact:

- How three relevant MVS contributed to a course on evidence-informed decision-making targeting the relevant roles (civil servants, knowledge brokers, and policymakers).
- How the MVS for undergraduate students contributed to a course targeting them and, in turn, how that experience informed a revision of the corresponding MVS.

⁴⁰ It was later decided not to pursue an MVS for Data Librarians solely as the essential skills and competences required to build a learning path for this group was sufficiently covered under the MVS for Data Stewards.

⁴¹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/collections-as-data-ig/work-statement/>

- How three relevant MVS (data steward, early career, and senior researchers) contributed to training for scholarly communications professionals, leading to interest in adoption of the MVS by research infrastructures.

4.3.1 Training Design for Evidence-Informed Decision Making

An example learning path comprising of seven courses that used the MVS in its development is that for “Open Science and Evidence-Informed Decision Making”. This learning path was developed for three MVS profiles: Policymaker, Civil Servant, and Knowledge Broker. The learning objectives covered a range of essential skills and competencies identified in each of the MVS, including understanding and applying open science principles and practices, navigating legal, ethical, and policy frameworks in Open Science, promoting collaboration, stakeholder engagement, and capacity building, and advancing Open Science through innovation and policy implementation. The learning objectives per course that were primarily inspired by the MVS are summarised in Table 3, which answers the first question presented in section [3.2.5](#).

“Open Science and Evidence-Informed Decision Making” Learning path	
Course Name	Learning Objectives
Course 1: Open Science is the new norm	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Define open science and its key principles. • Explain how open science enhances public trust in scientific research. • Demonstrate how open science practices improve accountability and transparency in research. • Compare the open science model with traditional closed science practices. • Define the legal and ethical principles that underpin open science.
Course 2: Ethical, Legal and Societal Implications (ELSI) and Data Governance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explain the challenges and opportunities within the EU regulatory framework for open science. • Demonstrate effective data governance practices for FAIR research. • Evaluate the impact of data governance on the quality and transparency of research. • Define the relationship between policy development and evidence in open science.
Course 3: Introduction to Evidence-informed Decision-making	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Describe the roles of various stakeholders in evidence-informed decision making. • Use open science outputs and tools to support decision making. • Interpret statistical data to extract meaningful insights for evidence-based decisions. • Identify key stakeholders involved in the open science ecosystem.
Course 4: Open Science Stakeholders and Collaboration Strategies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Describe the roles and interests of various open science stakeholders. • Describe the importance of collaboration and communication. • Apply engagement, collaboration and communication techniques to foster partnerships in open science.

Course 5: Empowering the Future of Research with Open Science	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluate the rationale for investing in Open Science and identify potential funding strategies. • Explain the importance of capacity building and training programs for open science. • Analyse how AI can be integrated into open science practices to enhance research and decision-making. • Describe how open science policies support open science practices.
Course 6: Open science policies support open science practices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Apply strategies to overcome challenges and barriers in adopting open science practices. • Analyse the cultural changes required to support open science adoption. • Evaluate the effectiveness of responsible research assessment frameworks. • Apply open science workflows in research practices.
Course 7: Implementing Open Science Policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Describe the essential elements for developing and implementing effective open science policies. • Adapt existing policies based on change of different circumstances.

Table 3 Learning Objectives of the Open Science and Evidence-Informed Decision Making Learning Path

Feedback on the MVS from the training task leader in response to the questions outlined in section 3.2.5 is given in [Appendix 2](#). It provided two key learning points:

- Confirmation that the MVS provides a clear outline of the essential and soft skills needed for the target audiences.
- The suggestion to have case studies that make use of the MVS for better understanding of each role and how the profiles can be used.

4.3.2 Training Design for Undergraduate Students

The Pilot Course for Undergraduate Students was designed to align with the MVS for undergraduate students. The alignment process was bidirectional. Initially, the alignment focused on matching the course's learning objectives with the MVS skills and competencies. The course content was designed to include all essential skills listed in the MVS (excluding soft skills).

Subsequently, developing the course materials allowed the task members to provide input into the MVS for undergraduate students, thereby facilitating co-creation. For instance, it was discovered during the course development that some skills deemed essential were missing from the original version of this MVS. This was echoed during the course feedback. Additionally, this task also reported on the learning objectives that extended beyond the MVS, which was also used to further refine the MVS for undergraduate students. These learning objectives were:

- Understand the basic concepts of intellectual property and copyright and their importance in scientific work
- Identify the principles of open licensing and the uses and implications of open licenses
- Know what is meant by the research impact
- Know the different types of impact indicators and how they work
- Understand the importance of research visibility and know different ways to increase the visibility of research

These learning objectives were incorporated into the 'Essential Skills' category of the undergraduate MVS.

4.3.3 Training Design for Scholarly Communications Professional

For the Scholarly Communications Professionals profile, it was acknowledged that the MVS had a positive influence by providing background information on key skills needed for the role. Contributors highlighted that the essential skills and competences were especially useful in shaping the structure and content of the course. The learning path was designed to support researchers across different levels of experience by integrating skills from both early career and senior researcher profiles. Participants indicated that updates to the training will align with the revised MVS and noted growing interest in the MVS from other organisations with a strong focus on scholarly communications, notably CESSDA and CLARIN.

4.4 Responses to the MVS Review Questionnaire

In April 2025, a survey⁴² aimed at external participants to check if the proposed profiles targeted the 'essential' learning outcomes appropriately for various roles was launched. There were 54 respondents to this Review questionnaire from 16 countries. Details of these, the kinds of organisation they were affiliated to are shown in Figures 7 and 8.

Figure 7 Responses to MVS questionnaire grouping 'country you are based in' by EU categories

Respondents' countries were grouped as follows: EU19: Austria, France, Germany, Ireland, Italy, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Spain, Sweden, UK. EU11: Bulgaria, Croatia. Candidate: North Macedonia; Non-EU: USA.

⁴² <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/5e7bd336-ba07-217f-59cd-15751649eb03>

The bias in the responses towards EU19 countries probably reflects the disproportionate number of established data professionals in these countries, and the resourcing available to their Research Performing Organisations. As Figure 8 shows most respondents indicate they were affiliated to these.

Figure 8 MVS questionnaire respondents by organisation type

Note that respondents were able to select 0-3 responses to the question in Figure 8, and of 54 respondents; 4 selected 3 types, 6 selected 2 types, and 16 did not select any.

The responses to rating scale questions are shown in Figures 9 and 10, showing that the MVS were considered by most respondents to match their expectations about OS skills, and to be usable in their own organisation.

Figure 9 Respondents views on how well MVS matched skills the role requires to practice OS

Figure 10 Respondents views on the usefulness of MVS for their own organisation

There were also qualitative responses to open questions. When reading the MVS for a particular role, the respondents first listed phrases summarising their own view on the main OS skills they would expect from skills for the role, then after reading the MVS proposed changes to it, they would recommended. Some also provided ‘further comments’. These are listed in [Appendix 3](#) to the report.

4.5 Wider Adoption of MVS: A Brief Example

A representative from the CSC RDM Competence Center in Finland delivered a series of lectures at the University of Tampere on March 21, 2025, utilizing the MVS for Data Steward for students enrolled in Data Steward education. The topic of the lectures was "What is a Data Steward and What Do They Do?"

The Zenodo document outlining the Minimum Viable Skillsets was provided to the students as pre-reading material. During the lectures, the mission, outcomes, activities, and essential skills of a Data Steward were presented as described in the document. After the presentation, students were asked to review the list of essential skills for Data Stewards. They were also asked to write comments on the Easyretro platform⁴³ about how they think each skill can be acquired, whether they already possess them, or if they can gain the skills through work experience. Following this, students were divided into groups to discuss skills necessary for data stewardship and the insights gained from the MVS.

The assignments generated a lot of comments and discussion. Some of the comments received include:

- "I think for me it is important to think, in what issues to specialize and not to try cover everything in detail."
- "It was good to realise that you can redirect your role and the skills you need. However, in a small organization you can have to do all sorts of things because resources are limited."

For the Data Steward profile, the feedback confirmed that the MVS can be used effectively as a learning resource, capturing the core competencies required for the role.

⁴³ <https://easyretro.io/>

5. Conclusions and Recommendations

5.1 MVS as Input to Training Design

Skills4EOSC has demonstrated the utility of MVS for capturing training requirements. In particular the MVS is a useful and relevant method for trainers to specify learning objectives for their target group, when designing learning paths and curricula for them.

All MVS were validated through internal feedback from training task leaders, with the exception of Legal Expert and Ethics Advisor. Broader community feedback on the latter was also sought. For all roles, potential reusers of any of the MVS profiles are encouraged to refer to the feedback reported as well to the MVS itself.

On the basis of feedback gathered from partners and the broader community of interest in Open Science skills, organisations are interested in adopting and reusing the MVS developed in the project, and consider these a valid representation of skills needed for the corresponding roles.

External validation for a wider range of MVS profiles should have been sought earlier, in future use the review questions to gather feedback from stakeholder groups before piloting training, rather than after.

5.2. Reflections from Community and Competence Centre Workshops

The authors have used various opportunities to discuss and enhance the co-creation of the MVS profiles. Some of these opportunities include a Competence Centres Network (CC Network) workshop in Berlin in October 2024 and participation at consecutive International Digital Curation Conferences in 2023 and 2024. In this section, two events are summarised: a WP5 led workshop in February 2025 and a CC network workshop in April 2025.

Feedback from the “Creating Thematic Recommendations for OS and RDM” Workshop

The WP5 workshop “Creating Thematic Recommendations for Open Science (OS) and Research Data Management (RDM)” took place in Milan in February 2025. Its aim was to co-develop thematic recommendations for integrating OS and FAIR RDM practices into research workflows, based on input from domain-specific communities and infrastructures. MVS were a cross-cutting theme throughout the workshop. Several task groups (T5.2–T5.6) included MVS elements in their draft recommendations, adapting profiles like those for researchers and Digital Collections Curators to disciplinary and institutional contexts. A dedicated hybrid session focused on adaptation strategies for MVS, with input from Competence Centres from Poland, Finland, Sweden, North Macedonia, Greece, France, and Germany, who shared perspectives on national training needs and approaches to MVS implementation.

The workshop **reaffirmed the relevance of the MVS** as a shared reference point for **training design** and profile development in OS and FAIR RDM. MVS-related elements were

integrated into thematic recommendations, and several CCs expressed interest in aligning the profiles with local training activities and strategic priorities.

Beyond their function in training design, the MVS profiles were also considered relevant for broader use cases such as **career development**, **role definition**, and **competence-based recruitment**. These applications were seen as opportunities to support institutional capacity-building and strategic workforce planning aligned with OS and FAIR RDM principles.

Building on this positive uptake, participants identified opportunities to further enhance the **practical usability** and **accessibility** of MVS materials. Discussions across thematic sessions and the dedicated adaptation workshop highlighted the value of distinguishing between **core competencies** and more **context-specific elements**. To support this, participants suggested rethinking the structure of profiles in a **more modular way** – enabling **flexible adaptation** by combining a stable core with **configurable components** aligned to institutional or disciplinary needs. For example, the profile of the **Research Infrastructure (RI) Professional** was discussed as covering a wide spectrum of sub-roles, such as repository managers, trainers, and IT staff. Participants highlighted that the skills and responsibilities associated with this profile may differ significantly, depending on institutional context and specific functions. This discussion opened a space for reflecting on how internal role variation might be more clearly addressed in future developments.

The workshop highlighted that CCs operate at different **levels of organisational maturity** and engagement. While some had already begun exploring how MVS could be applied in their context, others were encountering the profiles for the first time. Participants stressed the importance of providing **flexible entry points** and **differentiated support**, based on the local context and institutional capacity.

These discussions also revealed an opportunity to improve the accessibility of the MVS framework for **new stakeholders**. Some CCs had limited prior exposure to MVS, which underscored the potential value of additional **orientation materials** and **contextual explanations** to support broader understanding and engagement. Participants noted that this type of practical guidance could be further supported by explanatory resources clarifying **key terminology** and roles, especially in cases where profile descriptions rely on technical or infrastructure-specific vocabulary.

Participants also underlined that **emerging or less formalised CCs** may require more targeted support in adapting MVS to their local contexts. To address this, both thematic groups and CC representatives highlighted the value of **practical tools** such as annotated use cases, toolkits, and step-by-step guideline materials to help link MVS with **training pathways** and **institutional strategies**. These types of guidance were seen as essential for supporting **consistent and inclusive implementation** across different levels of organisational maturity.

The integration of MVS into both **formal** and **informal training** formats was also highlighted as a promising direction. Examples included PhD programmes, university-level courses, and lighter-touch activities such as OS cafés or self-paced learning modules, which were seen as complementary channels for wider **adoption** and **community participation**.

Looking ahead, participants encouraged continued investment in the **shared maintenance and governance** of the MVS framework. Suggestions included lightweight peer-review mechanisms, regular update cycles, and exploring alignment, where appropriate, with recognised reference frameworks. Participants saw value in keeping MVS a **living resource** – flexible and responsive – while continuing to develop it through shared practices, regular updates, and community feedback mechanisms.

The workshop confirmed that a core strength of the MVS approach lies in its **adaptability** and **openness to co-creation**. Participants saw value in maintaining this flexibility while complementing it with practical instruments, consistent communication, and ongoing collaboration across the Skills4EOSC community.

Feedback from the CC Network Workshop

As part of engagement activities under WP7, an April 2025 Competence Centres Network CC Network Workshop included a session on the MVS. The presentation provided an overview of the current MVS profiles, recent updates based on feedback, and results from the ongoing MVS review survey. This set the stage for an open discussion with CC representatives on how the MVS might be adapted and applied in their training contexts. To support the discussion, a live survey was used to gather participant input on MVS familiarity, perceived usefulness, and implementation prospects. Below is a synthesis of the key findings.

Familiarity with MVS varied across participants. Four respondents indicated that they were aware of the concept but not yet familiar with its details. Another four stated that they were familiar with some details but had not yet tried to use the approach. Two respondents noted that they had already applied MVS, for example to discuss learning outcomes for training. This gradient of experience underlines the emerging but still uneven understanding of the methodology across the CC Network.

Despite varying levels of prior engagement, all respondents who answered the relevant question expressed a **clear willingness to use the MVS approach** in training design.

Respondents identified several **strengths of the MVS** format: it enables data-driven validation of training content, supports continuous adaptation to evolving needs, and helps formulate task-driven and job-ready learning objectives. This reinforces MVS's role not as a prescriptive framework but as a flexible planning tool.

Suggestions for **improving the MVS** methodology as a tool for identifying learning outcomes were limited. Only one participant proposed making skill dependencies more explicit (e.g. "which skills rely on which others to function"). Another stated they could not think of anything to improve, while a third described MVS as already being "extremely useful tools," noting the difficulty of answering the question spontaneously.

A recurring theme across multiple responses was the **importance of local adaptation**. Most participants did not expect to use the Skills4EOSC courses "as-is," but instead saw value in

tailoring the content and structure to their institutional or national training priorities. Nonetheless, several noted the value of shared starting points and common vocabulary, especially in international collaborations. One respondent proposed a hybrid approach, starting with the core MVS profiles and localizing them based on the needs of computational sciences. Another likened the process to “forking” in software development – adapting a base version to suit specific use cases while maintaining alignment with shared principles.

Respondents also expressed a positive attitude towards **peer feedback and sharing**. One noted that “peers may spot gaps, overlaps or ambiguities that we missed,” and another indicated that while existing profiles served their purpose, feedback from others would still be welcome.

Key takeaways

The MVS developed within Skills4EOSC have demonstrated significant value as a foundation for OS training design, role definition, and organizational capacity-building. By articulating essential skills and competences, the MVS have supported trainers in designing targeted learning objectives, informed hiring processes for emerging OS roles, and provided a structured reference for CCs seeking to develop their internal expertise.

Feedback from training pilots, CCs, and professional networks confirms that the MVS approach effectively bridges the gap between high-level OS principles and the practical skills required across diverse domains. The flexibility of MVS allows them to be used not only in formal course development but also in modular training paths, informal upskilling activities, and workforce development strategies. Their relevance spans multiple roles, from early-career researchers and data stewards to research managers and policy advisors.

Building on these achievements, further work will strengthen the practical application of MVS by supporting adaptation processes to fit varied organizational contexts and disciplinary needs. While initial pilots validated the general structure and utility of MVS, experiences highlighted that successful adoption benefits from early stakeholder engagement, structured adaptation guidance, and continuous refinement based on thematic and institutional diversity. Moving forward, a systematic approach to adaptation, facilitation, and profile updates will be essential to maximize the long-term impact of the MVS Catalogue. The final section provides recommendations on improving and enhancing the use of the MVS.

5.2 Recommendations

5.2.1 Adapt and Adopt the MVS Methodology

Building on the experience gained in developing and applying the MVS, several lessons can guide their future use and evolution. While the project provided a strong foundation for skills development in OS, further steps could strengthen the impact and sustainability of the approach. The following directions are suggested to support the long-term adoption and adaptation of the MVS.

Further support adaptation:

Future initiatives may benefit from the development of a structured adaptation toolkit, providing guidance to CCs and training providers on how to customise MVS to local organisational contexts, different levels of OS maturity, and specific disciplinary requirements. Modular guidance could help maintain consistency with the core MVS structure, allowing for flexible use.

Expand thematic and career variations:

Future extensions of the MVS catalogue could align with the thematic development work conducted under WP5, supporting domain-specific adaptations for major research areas. Further refinement of career-stage distinctions, along with the integration of proficiency levels (e.g., basic, intermediate, advanced) for essential skills, would also enhance the practical relevance and usability of the profiles across different user groups.

Strengthen validation processes:

Future refinement of MVSs could incorporate earlier and broader external validation, engaging trainers, researchers, and institutional representatives in feedback cycles. This would help ensure that the profiles remain closely aligned with evolving skills needs and practical training applications. In particular, there is a need for further evaluation of the 'research user' MVS for the roles of civil servants, knowledge brokers, policymakers, and students.

Facilitate implementation through CC Network coordination:

The emerging Skills4EOSC CC Network, developed through WP7, could serve as a platform for structured peer-support mechanisms, enabling CCs to exchange experiences, co-develop adaptation strategies, and build collective capacity in applying MVS effectively.

The CC Network has an opportunity to build on the connections between MVS, particularly between similar competences across skillsets. It is notable that each of the MVS includes in its essential skills some element of training or mentoring. By making more explicit the connections between similar competences across different roles, the MVS could be used to facilitate peer learning. This may help address the imbalance between EU19 and EU11 countries in the maturity of established data professional roles in their Research Performing Organisations.

Ensure sustainability through governance:

Establishing an Editorial Interest Group could enable the continuous review, updating, and extension of the MVS catalogue, ensuring that it evolves alongside OS practices, technological developments, and changing policy landscapes. Example roles that can be included in future iterations of the MVS catalogue are the Research Software Engineer (RSE), Senior RSE, and Research Managers.

5.2.2 Establish a Sustainable MVS Editing & Review Process

Since the first iteration of this report, Skills4EOSC and this task has considered various ways in which to maintain the momentum of the development and use of the MVS after the project comes to a close. Via the Skills4EOSC Competence Centre Network, the establishment of an 'editorial board' has been proposed that comprises volunteers from the CC network community who, in addition to articulating the vision of the network and individual CCs, would work collaboratively to identify best ways to sustain key project outcomes, including the MVS. The way

in which the editorial board works to sustain via a review of newly created or adapted MVS profiles would be a matter of discussion within the network, but one proposed option has been the implementation of a dedicated OS Skills platform or journal that could invite the submission of skillsets, among other activities as it relates to skills development. It is expected that having a platform addressing OS skills could:

- Provide a means for the wider community to engage with the main outputs of the Skills4EOSC project
- Provide an opportunity to engage with the CC network as a go-to source for training and other skills development.
- Provide a means for CC participants to monitor and engage with community developments.
- Allow those engaged with using and developing outputs based on Skills4EOSC outputs to gain recognition for their contributions and professional development.

Overall, the sustainability and continued use of Skills4EOSC outputs remains a key priority. The CC Network will be a valuable means through which all outputs are sustained, adopted, and adapted to local contexts are required.

Appendix 1: MVS Design

The MVS are structured around four core elements or concepts that have been the subject of recent work to build skills for FAIR and Open Science, in the EOSC context and internationally. These are shown in Figure A1 and described further in Table A1.

Figure A1. Elements and Properties of a Minimum Viable Skillset

Definition	Min-Max (guideline)	Word length
Role: label summarising a mission that contributes to Open Science activities or outcomes, plus bullet-points listing kinds of organisation expected to fulfil these.	1 * per MVS	1-5
Mission: description of a role's scope or responsibility for performing activities leading to an OS Outcome, on behalf of a competence centre, organisation, or community.	1 per MVS	10-50
OS Activity: set of actions involved in performing essential skills and competences	3-9 per MVS	10-20
Essential skill or competence: statement describing either: Soft skill: personal attribute or aptitude required for the interpersonal, communication, or leadership dimensions of an activity, and which are improved with practice in the activity.	3-9 per MVS	5-20
Specialist competence: knowledge or skill required for the sector or domain-specific dimensions of an activity, including its legal, ethical and social aspects.		
Learning outcome: OS Skills term from published terminology, expressing the subject topic(s) of an essential skill or competence statement, at an appropriate level of granularity	1-5 per skill statement	2-3
OS Outcome: Open Science capability, output or objective that a role	1-6	5-20

may contribute to the implementation of by carrying out OS activities. per MVS

Table A1. Dictionary of MVS Elements

Typologies: competences and career stages

Introduction to Table A2 and this section of the appendix xxxxx

OS Competence dimensions

Technology	Developing and implementing processes to support systematic sharing of knowledge and tools, including measures to ensure open access to all digital research outputs.
Domain	Planning and implementing processes based on domain standards to ensure that research practices meet legal and ethical obligations, and that research outputs are reproducible.
Interpersonal	Developing open cooperative working relationships to involve all relevant knowledge actors in the co- creation of R&I agendas and contents
Communication	Planning, creating, editing, and delivering information relating to Open Science practices or policies to all relevant knowledge actors
Leadership	Development, advocacy, and evaluation of open science practices in collaborative R&I projects, programmes, or services.

Table A2. Dimensions of Open Science Competences

Proficiency levels

- Basic: awareness of the knowledge required to perform a skill.
- Intermediate: ability to perform a skill confidently and routinely with little or no supervision.
- Advanced: ability to supervise others in performing a skill, and to adapt the skill to meet complex and specialist needs.

Career stages

1. Student: an undergraduate or graduate student undertaking a taught degree course at a recognised higher education institution.
2. Research Actor: performs research as a PhD student or post-doc, or supports the research process undertaken by others, e.g. by providing services, making policy for research, or making policies that are informed by research results.
3. Senior Research Actor: has responsibilities for supervising research or practitioners who support research, or for leading implementation of Open Science within and across organisations.

Career stages 2 and 3 are intended to be consistent with the R1-R2 and R3-R4 stages (respectively) of the European Framework for Research Careers ⁴⁴.

44 European Commission DG Research & Innovation, (2011), Towards a European Framework for Research Careers https://cdn5.euraxess.org/sites/default/files/policy_library/towards_a_european_framework_for_research_careers_final.pdf

Notes

- Learning resource definition is from the Learning Resource Metadata Initiative (LRMI)
https://www.dublincore.org/specifications/lrmi/lrmi_terms/2020-11-12/#LearningResource
- Relevant learning resources may be tagged/identified with the relevant MVS but they do not need to be listed in the MVS itself.
- The model in Figure A1 is based on terms4FAIRskills. The main differences are as follows:
 - Mission is added, to be explicit about the scope of a role's function in relation to Open Science
 - Technical 'competence' is used instead of 'concept'
 - 'Open Science Outcome' instead of 'Data stewardship guideline'
 - Activities contribute to implementation of Outcomes
 - Learning outcome is used instead of 'medium'. This conceptually links the MVS to metadata standards for learning resources. The MVS identifies keywords terms for topics to enable the MVS to be used to find resources with matching terms in catalogues or registries that use the metadata standards (e. g. in EOSC portal).

Appendix 2. Internal Feedback on Policymaker MVS

This appendix provides the feedback on the MVS from the training task leader in response to the questions outlined in section 3.2.5. While the feedback addressed the Policymaker MVS, the course also drew on the Civil Servant and Honest Broker MVS.

Please answer the following questions-

1) Which learning path targets this role?

Please describe, including a url if available. _____

The learning path designed for policymakers, civil servants, and knowledge brokers is titled "Open Science and Evidence-Informed Decision Making." It is structured into seven courses, each addressing specific aspects of Open Science. The links to the relevant courses at the moment can be found here: <https://learning.skills4eosc.eu/course/index.php?categoryid=19>.

2) What learning objectives were defined for this learning path?

For each of the seven courses, we identified different learning objectives based on the area that was studied in each one. As this learning path is targeting all three profiles related to Open Science and Decision making, we decided to merge the courses as most of the material is related to all profiles, considering some modules could be used as additional information that was worth providing to everyone. If we can summarize the learning objectives of the entire learning path (of the 7 courses) these could be the following:

Understand and Apply Open Science Principles and Practices:

- Define Open Science, its principles, and its role in enhancing public trust, accountability, and transparency in research.
- Apply effective data governance practices aligned with FAIR principles to ensure reproducibility and transparency.

Navigate Legal, Ethical, and Policy Frameworks in Open Science:

- Analyze legal, ethical, and societal implications of Open Science within the EU regulatory framework and global contexts.
- Address challenges and opportunities in implementing Open Science policies and practices.

Promote Collaboration, Stakeholder Engagement, and Capacity Building:

- Engage and collaborate with diverse stakeholders to foster partnerships and build a culture of openness.
- Develop strategies for capacity building, training, and overcoming barriers to Open Science adoption.

Advance Open Science through Innovation and Policy Implementation

- Explore the integration of emerging technologies, such as AI, to enhance research and decision-making in Open Science.
- Design and implement effective Open Science policies and workflows, ensuring alignment with institutional and societal needs.

The analysis of the learning objectives per course is provided in the following table:

"Open Science and Evidence-Informed Decision Making" Learning path

Course Name	Learning Objectives
EIDM Train of Trainers Co-1: "Open Science is the norm"	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Define open science and its key principles. • Explain how open science enhances public trust in scientific research. • Demonstrate how open science practices improve accountability and transparency • Compare the open science model with traditional closed science practices. • Define the legal and ethical principles that underpin open science.
EIDM Train of Trainers Co-2: "Ethical, Legal and Sociopen science. Implications (ELSI) and Governance"	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explain the challenges and opportunities within the EU regulatory framework • Demonstrate effective data governance practices for FAIR research. • Evaluate the impact of data governance on the quality and transparency of

research.

- Define the relationship between policy development and evidence in open science.
- Describe the roles of various stakeholders in evidence-informed decision making.

EIDM Train of Trainers Co· Use open science outputs and tools to support decision making.

3: "Introduction to Evidence-based Decision-making"· Interpret statistical data to extract meaningful insights for evidence-based informed Decision-making decisions.

- Identify key stakeholders involved in the open science ecosystem.

EIDM Train of Trainers Co· Describe the roles and interests of various open science stakeholders.

4: "Open Science Stakeholders and Collaboration Strategies"

- Describe the importance of collaboration and communication.
- Apply engagement, collaboration and communication techniques to foster partnerships in open science.

- Evaluate the rationale for investing in Open Science and identify potential funding strategies.

- Explain the importance of capacity building and training programs for open science.

EIDM Train of Trainers Co· science.

5: "Empowering the Future of Research with Open Science and decision-making"· Analyze how AI can be integrated into open science practices to enhance research and decision-making.

- Describe how open science policies support open science practices.

EIDM Train of Trainers Co· Apply strategies to overcome challenges and barriers in adopting open science practices.

6: "Open science policies support open science practices"

- Analyze the cultural changes required to support open science adoption.
- Evaluate the effectiveness of responsible research assessment frameworks.
- Apply open science workflows in research practices.

EIDM Train of Trainers Co· Describe the essential elements for developing and implementing effective open science policies.

7: "Implementing Open Science Policies"

- Adapt existing policies based on change of different circumstances.

Please note, that each course consists of many modules, with different learning objectives per module and lecture – the above table is also a summary of the main learning objectives described in the developed modules and submodules.

3) Which of the following statements best describes how the MVS was used when the learning objectives were defined?

Please identify any of the statements below that may be relevant.

- Learning objectives were defined without referring to the MVS.
- The MVS indirectly influenced the learning objectives by providing background information on skills that are considered essential to the role.
- Were substantially based on the MVS, e.g. used similar wording.

4) What aspects of the MVS were most and least useful for designing the learning path?

- Most useful : The MVS provided a clear outline of the essential (but also soft) skills needed for policymakers, enabling the development of targeted Key Messages first and then Learning Objectives. Moreover, its structure helped align course content with expected competences, not only related to Open Science, but also based on their Main Role Activities.
- Least useful : I think the analysis of the Essential Skills and Main Activities/Contributions to OS helped a lot to identify Learning Objectives for the course. The OS Skills terms were not used during the preparation of the curriculum, but I guess if I had to prepare a course at the moment I would probably need some of them – a very big number of skills sometimes is a bit overwhelming, but I understand the purpose of adding them for further information.

5) What lessons should WP2 learn, based on your experience of using the MVS?

It would be very helpful if the MVS could provide some role-specific practical examples, such as case studies or real-world scenarios for better understanding of each role and the different situations that they come across during their workday.

6) How well do the proposed 'key Open science skills terms' represent the essential skills for this MVS?

Skills are well represented	I think the skills are very well represented	c	c	c	c	Skills are poorly represented
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Which skills need to be better represented, if any? N/A

Are there others terms in ESCO, ResearchComp, or terms4FAIRskills that would better represent these skills? If so, please list them here.

I think there are so many terms for skills, for sure there might be more but I think there are already too many provided, so I wouldn't add more. In the second role of PM (Evidence Role), I think we could use more terms from the Civil Servant profile, as they both are requested to use data in a similar way, as mentioned in their essential skills and main activities.

7) Are you aware of any organisations, projects or other initiatives interested in using the MVS for their skills development?

The MVS should be a resource that complements the learning materials delivered by your WP. Trainers adopting your training can potentially also reuse the MVS to assess how the role can be developed alongside the skills of the people involved. We would very much appreciate any information you can share about interest in applying the MVS. Organisations may be directly involved in Skills4EOSC or not.

I think we could share the MVS for the profiles that we have prepared the training for, as additional material (handouts or templates) that could be included in the course for further use.

Appendix 3. Feedback from Review Questionnaire

The feedback provided below comes from the Review Questionnaire launched in April 2025. Respondents were asked to consider the main skills needed for a respective profile before reading the MVS and then consider what might be missing after reading the profile.

Civil Servant

Respondent views on 'main skills' stated before reading the MVS

- Knowledge of publishing dynamics, awareness that the purpose of one's work is the public good.
- Proficiency in translating complex scientific concepts into accessible language for non-specialist audiences and building networks to collaborate with researchers and stakeholders.
- Ability to analyse, and utilize data for evidence-based decision

Any changes recommended after reading the MVS

- None

Any 'further comments'

- No responses

Data Steward

Respondent views on 'main skills' stated before reading the MVS

- Open science role must have a cross-disciplinary profile with experience in the world of research, with great skills in the field of Open Access, Open Data and FAIR data, but with a broad view of everything that surrounds open science: infrastructures, citizen science, open knowledge (education & skills, future scholarly communication), new metrics, incentives... The role also involves promoting open science and researcher capacity, communication and pedagogy are crucial skills.
- Communication skills, ease of learning, knowledge of data management regulations and best practices, openness to sharing knowledge, trainers' skills.
- Explain SO policy in general and translate it in the specific domain of the project / people
- Knowledge of the complete cycle of life of data.
- Knowledge of the general aspects of law an ethically on data.
- Knowledge of DMP.
- Patience and good people skills.
- Disciplinary experience on RDM, good communication skills, good organizational skills, RDM and OS experience, advocacy, training, networking skills, good management skills.
- Data engineering, data management, open data, DBA.
- Customer focus, good judgement, analytical skills, kindness, adaptable.
- Understanding of the research landscape, Open Research practices generally, international and national policies. People skills to engage with stakeholders. Presentation and problem-solving skills.

Any changes recommended after reading the MVS

- I think not, that the essential and transversal skills are well defined.
- Would be good to include knowledge of data structuring as well as metadata - e.g. understanding different types of database (and what you can do with them); data cleaning techniques / data wrangling; anonymization and pseudonymization (and how much anonymization is required in order to be able to share data at different levels of access control).
- The domain specific skills listed are not all essential but rather a pick list of what applicants might become involved in.
- If this is to be used in a hiring criteria then yes. You won't get diverse hires based on the above: it's too specific. Knowledge about RDM can be learned in the job with good training. The most essential to me is them understanding research.

Any 'further comments'

- Sounds really good.
- [It] would be more inclusionary (from an English-speaking background) to use Open Research not Open Science.

Digital Collections Curator

Respondent views on 'main skills' stated before reading the MVS

- Knowledge about OS, FAIR principles, long-term preservation, evaluation skills, advocacy skills, high-level technological proficiency.
- Good knowledge about rich metadata need to describe the research outputs and datasets or other digital objects.
- Understand infrastructures available at the organization or outside in open access to make those outputs discoverable and reusable, supporting dissemination and collaboration.
- Understand the research life cycle to identify important actions to support researchers.
Communication skills and the ability to build bridges between researchers and technical team.
- Ability to quickly understand and use new tools and standards, and to clearly communicate their advantages.
- Excellent communication skills - training, presentations, guidance writing.
- Self-confidence - ability to "hold their own" with researchers.
- Ability to interpret and explain policies.
- Strong advocacy skills.
- Strong organisational skills.
- General knowledge of Open Science and FAIR principles.
- General knowledge of data repository and open archives.

Any changes recommended after reading the MVS

- Sounds reasonable. Maybe high-level technological proficiency should be considered.
- None
- I don't think this role needs to have the skills themselves to do data migration - what they do need is the knowledge that this is necessary, and access to appropriate resources. I don't think that decolonisation activities need be part of this MVS.

Any 'further comments'

- No responses

Ethics Advisor

Respondent views on 'main skills' stated before reading the MVS

- Good understanding of data sharing and open research mandates. Understanding of 'early' processes that facilitate data sharing later in the process. Understanding of interplay of ethics, RDM, IP and data protection.

Any changes recommended after reading the MVS

- None - I think it's a good, comprehensive list.

Any 'further comments'

- I would advocate strongly for the use of 'Open Research' instead of 'Open Science'. We use this phrase as an institution as it allows us to better connect with non-science disciplines and reduces alienation of researchers working in non-scientific research.

Knowledge Broker

Respondent views on 'main skills' stated before reading the MVS

- Being aware of relevant developments; listen well.
- Critical understanding of scientific output, good communication skills (e.g, body language, ability to translate technical concepts into daily language), empathy and creativity.
- Broad knowledge of sciences, intense curiosity, ability to generalize patterns, "egoless" engagement.
- Curiosity, knowledge of all different roles, ability to reformulate wording depending on audience, ability to link science with society priorities, understanding science and policy-makers culture.

Any changes recommended after reading the MVS

- No responses

Any 'further comments'

- No responses

Legal Expert

Respondent views on 'main skills' stated before reading the MVS

- Good communication skills, ability to understand the bigger picture of Open Science.
- Solution oriented mindset.

Any changes recommended after reading the MVS

- No, the above-mentioned are good.
- Skills related to intellectual property should be added. As mentioned in the first paragraph, "privacy, intellectual property, and contractual obligations" are all equally important (I require expert support esp. on the reuse of existing IP often).

Any 'further comments'

- Perhaps too much emphasis on Open Science in the profile? Some legal profiles (e.g. GDPR experts, DPO) can contribute to healthy institutional Open Science policies without being themselves promoters of Open Science. They need to be aware of the context and on board with it, but in my experience they do not necessarily need to advocate for Open Science. Their contribution is valuable as is, because it is specific.

Policymaker for Research

Respondent views on 'main skills' stated before reading the MVS

- Knowledge of the field of SSH, ability to identify concrete actions to be taken for the dissemination and application of open science in the said field, given a greater inherent difficulty in dealing with data than in the hard sciences.

Any changes recommended after reading the MVS

- No responses

Any 'further comments'

- No responses

Policymaker – Evidence based

- No responses

Researcher - Early Career

Respondent views on 'main skills' stated before reading the MVS

- Understanding open science principles, confidence in open access publishing, skills in research data management, knowledge about sharing data responsibly, documenting research protocols and workflows clearly, collaborative research skills, skills in designing participatory research projects such as citizen science, science communication skills, use of open tools and platforms and knowledge about where to find them, participating in open peer review processes, awareness of policies.
- Understands funder policies; Awareness of institutional and national/international infrastructure and tools supporting open research; Good advocate/communicator.
- It is very important for R1 and R2 researchers to have a general understanding of all facets of Open Science skills. They need first to recognize the role of managing open data - FAIR and all other elements. In the list below, I miss some skills related to emotional intelligence - the capability to explain and speak about your research in an emotionally engaging way but at the same time to be able to recognize the audience's interests and capacity to understand. OS should have human face/heart.
- Motivation and buy-in of the OA benefits; understand data, metadata, interoperability; licenses FOSS; communication; data protection and other data-related regulations.
- Awareness of publishing in their area, Awareness of disciplinary research practice and apply that to open science. Awareness of ethics and integrity in terms of what can be open and what needs to stay closed.

Any changes recommended after reading the MVS

- Science communication within the scientific community and outside; stakeholder engagement with public, industry and policy; skills in inter- and transdisciplinary (research) projects.
- Several of the 'essential' skills seem like they should be 'desirable'. It seems a lot to expect an early career researcher to be an expert in understanding all the legal aspects of research, as well as have entrepreneurial skills in applying for OS funding. To expect all these things on top of doing research would require a lot of time, and would need adequate reward for putting in the time e.g. recognition via REF in the UK.
- No changes, but emotional intelligence skills should be added.
- Possibly more aligned to STEMM than AHSS e.g. no acknowledgement of closed research, plus entrepreneurial skills. Commitment to undertaking training on on digital-oriented research practices needs to change. A lot here that is on top of main role.

- Ability to assess FAIRness of existing data, and to capture, process, analyse, and preserve data according to OS principles. This should be changed to ability to assess FAIRness of any type of research output, not just data.

Any 'further comments'

- Is this a full-time research role or is there time assigned for OS-related duties such as the training of others?
- Add something about the possible impact on policy-making, both via the results of research but also with the development of policy recommendations (researchers with legal, political science, economic background).
- We could not use this as is in our own organisation and would need to change. Also unclear how we would do this at institutional level.

Researcher- Senior

Respondent views on 'main skills' stated before reading the MVS

- Have a network - know whom to ask; know the landscape, that it - be aware of the central bodies necessary to engage.
- Be able to implement open science principles in their own specific discipline; transfer open science practices to younger researchers and students; be able to quantify the practical use of open science when evaluating students and young researchers.
- How to correctly apply open science practices in all the context of the digital objects involved in the process of implementing research results.

Any changes recommended after reading the MVS

- The list is good.
- Just very small comments: consider rephrasing the verbs to be unified (e.g. realise versus applying, use realise and apply). From this aspect "developing" would become something like "continuous development or advanced application".
- I am not sure it is reasonable to expect expert awareness of legal aspects. They should listen to expert advice on this. In fact, in general good networks with other actors such as RDM experts would be a useful attribute.
- Ability to disseminate knowledge.

Any 'further comments'

- No responses

RI Professional

Respondent views on 'main skills' stated before reading the MVS

- Knowledge of open science and FAIR, technical skills, understanding of how language resources are compiled, managed, processed, shared and archived, project management skills, people skills, communication and event management skills, leadership skills, awareness and ability to understand the ethical and legal aspects related to research data.
- Expertise in open science, research Integrity, Responsible conduct of research, knowledge of National and European regulations and policies for open science FAIR data, Knowledge of institutional policies and Infrastructure, Domain specific knowledge, GDPR, Data confidentiality. IP, Knowledge transfer, Database / repository management skills.
- Knowledge of domain open standards and use cases. Ability to bridge researchers requirements with technical developers. Knowledge of general and specific metadata schemata. Ability in data and metadata management.
- Fair data implementation, ability to understand ethical and legal implications, responsible use of data-driven technologies, knowledge of diverse EU research policies and systems.
- IT competence, awareness of the essential current trends of science, general open-mindedness.
- Monitor, design and develop policy and governance strategies for Open Access, Research Data Management, Research Metrics and Digital Scholarship.
- The skills this person would need include: metadata knowledge, API and integration knowledge, communication and "code switching" ability.

Any changes recommended after reading the MVS

- As a training officer, I do not think I need to tick all the boxes. Maybe the RI professional can be further refined in the following sub-profiles: scientific director; technical director; management assistant; legal and ethical expert; finance officer; communication and policy officer; events manager; training and education officer; developer; repository manager; data steward.

- I would add Knowledge of institutional policies and Infrastructure, Domain specific knowledge, to the skills required.
- I know Pedagogical skills are included but I would strengthen Sharing knowledge and processes by referencing training design.
- I think they all apply.
- Would add managing and analysing data into the above.
- n/a

Any 'further comments'

- I select the first option because the profile is general enough to identify the basic skills and knowledge of an RI professional would need to have. However, it will not help me much in identifying the training needs in my own organisation because we have different profiles for the service, support and coordination roles. Someone in a coordination or supportive role does not really need to know about the technical infrastructure and computing systems, whereas an IT manager is not supposed to set up training programmes and have pedagogical skills.
- The main activities seem to be describing a senior level of responsibility. I would see junior levels also inhabiting this role.

Scholarly Communications Professional

Respondent views on 'main skills' stated before reading the MVS

- Ability to learn and adapt well, good knowledge of open access publishing processes, high research integrity standards, good knowledge of editorial work and peer review processes, knowledge of bibliometrics and altmetrics, overview of open science practices in the EU.
- A broad understanding of the schol comm landscape and its opportunities and challenges, including (open) access and financial models, services and platforms, legal aspect, good practices and standards (e.g. FAIR, trusted repositories).
- Knowledge of: open publication models, copyright related issues, open repositories, research assessment, the way research is conducted.

Any changes recommended after reading the MVS

- Knowledge of how to address ethical issues, good knowledge of editorial work and peer review processes, ability to implement EDI principles and Sustainable Development Goals, good knowledge of Open Science policies.
- Knowledge of long-term accessibility, documentation and archiving of research outputs (cf. Laakso et al., Open is not forever. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.24460>).

Any 'further comments'

- No responses

Student – Masters

- No responses

Student – Undergraduate

- No responses

Appendix 4. Acknowledgments

The following people contributed a response to the MVS review questionnaire and provided their names to be acknowledged in this report:

Albena Antonova, Isabelle Biagiotti, Brian Cahill, Margherita Carpani, Sonja Filiposka, Isolde Gottwald, Todor Gurov, Adamantios Koumpis, Mikołaj Leszczuk, Máiréad Murray, Alice Orrù, Carmeb Reverté , James A J Wilson.

Skills 4 eosc

Annex to D2.6 Catalogue of OS career profiles and MVS - update

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Deliverable Abstract

This Annex to D2.6 offers examples of Minimum Viable Skillset (MVS) Profiles. Each MVS describes key skills and competences for a role involved in practising Open Science (OS) with the support of the EOOSC. MVS Profiles are synthesised from established competences frameworks and resources. They are proposed as an aid to skills development, especially curriculum and course design. Each MVS Profile relates a skillset to the Open Science (OS) practices, activities, and outcomes that may typically be expected of the role concerned. The methodology is further described in the main D2.6 report.

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DELIVERY SLIP ¹

Date	Name	Partner/Activity	Date
<i>From:</i>	Angus Whyte	UEDIN/ T2.1	17.06.2025
<i>Moderated by:</i>	Dominique Green	UEDIN/ WP2	25.06.2025
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	Sara Casati	ELSI WP	08.05.2023
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	Valentina Colcelli	ELSI WP	08.05.2023
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<i>Contributor:</i>	Luca Schirru	KU/ ELSI WP	08.05.2023
<i>Contributor:</i>	Irakleitos Souyioultzoglou	OPERAS/WP5	08.05.2023
<i>Contributor:</i>	Claire Sowinski	INIST- CNRS/ T2.1	08.05.2023
<i>Contributor:</i>	Gabriela Torres Ramos	INIST- CNRS/ T2.1	08.05.2023
<i>Contributor:</i>	Nida van Leersum	TU-DELFT/ T2.1	08.05.2023
	Bernd Saurugger	WP5	08.05.2023
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	Lorna Wildgaard	WP6	08.05.2023
<i>Reviewed by:</i>	Clara Lines Diaz	UEDIN/WP5	24.06.2025
<i>Reviewed by:</i>	Dominique Green	UEDIN/WP2	26.06.2025
<i>Approved by:</i>	Claudio Prandoni, Sara Di Giorgio	GARR	30.06.2025

¹ As this is the updated version of this catalogue, the original contributions with initial contribution dates are kept. Please see each individual profile for latter adjustments made after internal and external reviews and template updates.

DOCUMENT LOG

Issue	Date	Comment	Author
v.0.1	8.5.2023	Initial draft based on D2.1 report, community feedback, internally reviewed MVS drafts, and updates as per D2.6	Angus Whyte [lead] and co-authors above
v.1.0	30.6.2023	Draft updated following internal review	As above
v.1.1	24.06.2025	Catalogue collated with updated versions of MVS profiles	Clara Lines Diaz

LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS²

CARE	Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, and Ethics
CSCCE	Centre for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement
DMP	Data Management Plan
ELSI	Ethical, Legal and Social Issues
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ETHRD IG	Education and Training on Handling of Research Data Interest Group (RDA)
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IT	Information Technology
JRC	Joint Research Centre
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
MVS	Minimum Viable Skillset
ORCC	Open Research Competencies Coalition
OS	Open Science
R&I	Research and Innovation
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RDM	Research Data Management
RI	Research Infrastructure
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
RSE	Research Software Engineer
T4fs	Terms for FAIR skills

² See also EOSC Glossary: EOSC Glossary Interest Group. (2020). EOSC Glossary (December 2020). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4472643>.

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Introduction

This Annex to the Skills4EOSC D2.6 Catalogue of Open Science Career Profiles and Minimum Viable Skillsets: update provides the content of the MVS Profiles for selected roles involved in performing and enabling Open Science.

As described in the main report, the catalogue currently offers the following MVS Profiles:

MVS Title (Role)
Civil Servant
Data Stewards - Coordinator, Embedded
Digital Collections Curator
Ethics Advisor
Knowledge Broker
Legal Expert
Policymaker - Evidence-based policymaker
Policymaker - Research Policy
Researcher - Early Career
Researcher - Senior
Research Infrastructure Professional
Scholarly Communications Professional
Student - Masters Level
Student - Undergraduate

Table 1. Current MVS catalogue entries, with variations

Civil Servant

V0.3 2025

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Issue	Date	Comment	Author
0.1	June 2023	Final draft for D2.1	Emma Lazzeri, Sara di Giorgio, Dominique Green, Claire Sowinski, Gabriela Torres Ramos, Betty Evangelinou, Bojana Koteska
0.2	October 2024	Restructured to add ESCO terms and highlight essential skills	Bojana Koteska
0.3	June 2025	Alignment with survey texts Removed non-essential ESCO terms	Claire Sowinski, Angus Whyte

Introduction: Open Science mission for this role

The Minimum Viable Skillset (MVS) sets out to describe a shared framework for recognizing the competencies required for civil servants engaged in advancing Open Science. Civil servants are typically employed by Ministers in government departments, where they perform a wide range of administrative, regulatory, or policy-related functions. Civil servants execute the Executive power of the State and play a critical role in ensuring that government operations run smoothly. Although the nature of civil service employment may vary by country and specific role, common positions include clerks, analysts, policy advisors, inspectors, and managers.

Civil servants act as central figures in the execution of government policies and administration. They are responsible for implementing and upholding government regulations, ensuring that public sector bodies operate according to established frameworks and guidelines. Civil servants also play a role in promoting transparency and accountability, particularly in the context of Open Science, by facilitating the appropriate access to and re-use of scientific data for public benefit. They ensure that administrative processes are neutral, non-partisan, and aligned with ethical standards.

One important aspect of civil service employment is that it is typically non-political. Civil servants are expected to remain neutral and non-partisan in their work, ensuring that public sector organizations operate fairly and effectively, free from political bias or favoritism. This neutrality allows them to carry out their duties impartially, maintaining the trust and confidence of the public.

Civil servants create and support open access to scientific knowledge, data, and research results, serving the public interest through the appropriate re-use of data produced and shared by research actions. By embedding Open Science principles into their work, civil servants ensure that the research data generated by various institutions is accessible and reusable, contributing to policy-making, innovation, and public benefit.

In their roles, civil servants uphold Open Science values such as transparency, ethical data use, and accessibility. They act as facilitators in connecting research outcomes with public policy, ensuring that scientific data informs government decisions and serves the public good. Their work supports

evidence-based decision-making and aligns with the mission of promoting Open Science for societal benefit.

Civil Servant

Associated function titles: Civil Servant, Public Policy Advisor, Government Analyst, Administrative Officer, Policy Coordinator, Regulatory Specialist.

Essential Skills for this Role

- Good understanding of OS principles and practices, open data, open research, and open access.
- Developing policies and guidelines that promote OS.
- Solid understanding of OS research ethics
- Being familiar with technology and tools used to support OS practices.
- Managing projects related to OS.
- Providing training and education to researchers, policymakers, and public citizens about OS practices.
- Evaluating the impact of OS practices and making recommendations for future improvement.
- Good understanding of (personal and non-personal) data management, including data storing, analysis, and sharing according to the FAIR and OS principles.
- Good understanding of the regulatory framework (national, regional, and international) concerning intellectual property rights (e.g., copyrights and trade secrets) and other non-personal data (e.g., research data and data held by Public Sector bodies). As an example, in the regional level, this may include, but not be limited to, the Open Data Directive, the Data Governance Act, and the Directives and Regulations concerning Copyrights and Trade Secrets in the EU.

Soft / Transversal Skills - considered equally important by Skills4EOSC, these are not specific to the occupation or sector.

- Communication
- Collaboration
- Leadership
- Citizen Engagement
- Negotiation and diplomacy
- Innovative thinking
- Strategic and analytical skills
- Teamwork
- Adaptability to changes

Background assumptions

Main activities

- Clarify and shape OS strategy and priorities for the national and international interest
- Involve and engage the right stakeholders and partners in making recommendations or decisions on OS
- Shape strategies and plans which help put into practice OS (give a long-term direction)
- Develop the capabilities in OS of the staff
- Engage in the open research process
- Ensure compliance with ethical, legal, and regulatory criteria
- Communicate / actively promote OS
- Facilitate the engagement of different stakeholders in co-creation actions

Contributes to which Open Science outcomes?

- Research is more transparent, accessible, and reproducible.
- Collaboration and knowledge sharing within the scientific community and beyond.
- Scientific knowledge and research results are openly available, to ensure that taxpayers' money is being used effectively and efficiently, and that the benefits of research are being shared widely.
- Policies that support open access to research publications and data are implemented, encouraging researchers to make their work openly available.
- Collaboration and knowledge-sharing is facilitated between researchers, government agencies, and the public.
- Open science practices are promoted through training and education, and engaging with stakeholders to understand their needs and priorities.
- Decision-making re-uses data that has been produced and shared by research actions.

Further information

Contributors: Emma Lazzeri, Sara di Giorgio, Dominique Green, Claire Sowinski, Gabriela Torres Ramos, Betty Evangelinou, Bojana Koteska

Open Science skills terms

OS skills terms match the essential skills in this MVS to competence definitions from relevant taxonomies. The selected terms offer further information to help identify the learning objectives for skills development. Sources: European Skills, Competences and Occupations ontology ([ESCO](#)), [ResearchComp](#), [terms4FAIRskills](#), [Center Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement](#).

ESCO Research Skills: [Manage open publications](#); [Manage findable accessible interoperable and reusable data](#); [Increase the impact of science on policy and society](#); [Apply research ethics and scientific integrity principles in research activities](#); [Perform project management](#); [Mentor individuals](#); [Promote the transfer of knowledge](#); [Synthesise information](#); [Manage research data](#); [Manage intellectual property rights](#); [Interact professionally in research and professional environments](#); [Promote the participation of citizens in scientific and research activities](#).

ESCO Transversal Skills: [Participate actively in civic life](#); [Exercise rights and responsibilities](#); [Manage time](#); [Plan](#); [Communicate with a non-scientific audience](#); [Comply with regulations](#); [Moderate a discussion](#); [Address an audience](#); [Build networks](#); [Work in teams](#); [Show initiative](#); [Advise others](#); [Lead others](#); [Make decisions](#); [Motivate others](#); [Show confidence](#); [Resolve conflicts](#); [Show empathy](#); [Negotiate compromises](#); [Demonstrate intercultural competence](#); [Think creatively](#); [Manage frustration](#); [Approach challenges positively](#); [Think innovatively](#); [Keep an open mind](#); [Think analytically](#); [Solve problems](#); [Build team spirit](#); [Adapt to change](#); [Demonstrate willingness to learn](#).

ResearchComp: [Manage research data](#); [Promote open access publishing](#); [Operate open source software](#); [Mobilise resources](#); [Creativity](#); [Communicate to the broad public](#); [Promote the transfer of knowledge](#); [Teach in academic or vocational contexts](#); [Interact professionally](#); [Interact professionally](#); [Work in teams](#); [Negotiate](#); [Promote citizen science](#); [Creativity](#); [Analytical thinking](#); [Strategic thinking](#).

Terms4FAIRskills: [Open access publishing](#); [Data sharing and publication](#); [Assessment on FAIR data criteria](#); [Information governance](#); [Data policy](#); [Persistent identifiers management](#); [Resource management](#); [Data sharing and publication](#); [Data governance](#); [Information security](#).

CSCCE: [Advocacy](#); [Consultation and listening](#); [Content creation and curation](#); [Content planning](#); [Landscape analysis](#); [Proposal development](#); [Technical support](#); [Financial management](#); [Operational planning and implementation](#); [Record-keeping](#); [Teaching and training](#); [Speaking and presenting](#); [Evaluation and assessment](#); [Media relations](#); [Collaboration](#); [Meeting facilitation](#); [Engagement](#); [Knowledge brokering](#); [Outreach](#).

Reference sources

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Data Stewards

V1.1 2025

DOCUMENT LOG

Issue	Date	Comment	Author
0.1	13/02/2023	Initial content	Angus Whyte, Nida van Leersum, Päivi Rauste, Bojana Koteska, Laurence Horton
0.2	14/03/2023	Revised draft for discussion	as above
0.3	28/03/2023	Further revision responding to comments	as above, Karsten Kryger Hansen
0.4	1/05/2023	Further revision	as above
0.5	1/05/2023	Structured to reflect dual nature of role, responding to comments from critical friends, Data Steward Networks	Nida van Leersum, Päivi Rauste, Bojana Koteska, Laurence Horton, Angus Whyte
0.6	12/5/2023	Finalisation of the MVS draft	as above
0.7	1/10/2024	Revised to add ESCO terms and respond to feedback on training pilot	Angus Whyte, Nida van Leersum, Bojana Koteska, Laurence Horton.
0.8	7/10/2024	Restructured to reduce duplication, with WP4 input	Angus Whyte, Nida van Leersum, Lorna Wildgaard
0.9	14/10/2024	Skills terms linked to sources	Angus Whyte
1.0	11/02/2025	Skills termed edited in response to feedback (NvL, LW)	Angus Whyte
1.1	30-04-2025	Alignment with survey texts Removed non-essential terms	Sowinski Claire, Angus Whyte

Introduction: Open Science mission for this role

The Minimum Viable Skillset (MVS) sets out to describe competencies required for Open Science practitioner roles. Data Stewards put Open Science principles into practice and are a key role for the European Open Science Cloud. The MVS includes two variations of the role, one described as 'Coordinator' and the other 'Embedded'.

These represent two ends of a spectrum, with 'Coordinator' describing a role providing support across an organisation's research domains and units, and 'Embedded' describing a role close to a research team and to its domain-specific practices. We acknowledge that these roles can overlap, influenced by the availability of resources, and by disciplinary and organisational cultures. Data Stewardship expertise is typically distributed across a team, drawing on in-house capabilities and

external services provided to the Research Performing Organisation, e.g. by Research Infrastructures, Service Providers (e.g. scholarly communications), and Competence Centres.

In general terms, Data Stewards work with stakeholders to establish, govern and maintain processes to collect research data, make it usable for research objectives, facilitate its transformation into research output, assist in quality assurance, and support informed decision-making on its openness for reuse according to ethical, legal and social expectations.

In the EOSC specifically, in their roles as practitioners and champions of Open Science, trainers, and enablers of others in their organisation, Data Stewards are likely to be both consumers and providers of EOSC services or resources.

Coordinator Data Steward	Embedded Data Steward
<p>Coordinator Data Stewards act as a ‘centralised knowledge and communication hub’ for researchers. They advise and train on policy, guidelines, data management plans, institutional infrastructure and tools to implement FAIR and CARE principles across the organisation.</p> <p>Associated function titles: Data Steward, Data Librarian, Research Data Management Specialist, Research Data Manager, Research Data Management Consultant, Reproducibility Librarian.</p>	<p>Embedded Data Stewards serve research teams, faculties, departments, sections of organisations directly involved in producing research outputs, supporting them to plan and implement FAIR and CARE principles, meeting needs of researchers as they arise, and working with others to ensure outputs are preserved and reusable in the long term.</p> <p>Associated function titles: Data Steward, Data Manager, Data Curator, Research Data Manager</p>
<p>Essential Skills for this Role</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cross-domain/domain-specific knowledge of Open Science practices, policies, and regulations, translating these (when necessary) to the appropriate levels of the organisation. • Service provision to support cross-domain/domain-specific Open Science practices including: use of FAIR and CARE principles, Open Access, data optimization, data preservation, archiving, and responsible re-use. • Knowledge about Research Data Management, (personal) data governance and ethics, Open Science data publication and exchange (sharing) services, information security, and risk management. • Raising awareness of the value of good data management among data creators and users, researchers, organisational colleagues, and decision-makers. • Advising and providing support on the use of infrastructure and tools at the appropriate levels of the organisation, e.g., for data storage, data versioning, and documentation, FAIR software, and databases. • Designing and delivering training to support Open Science practices, policies, and practices. • Monitoring the research and funding ecosystem, including possible conflicting 	

motivations, drivers, and incentives among different stakeholders.

- **Knowledge/awareness of programming**, FAIR code, and FAIR software, and use of standards and ontologies.

Soft / Transversal Skills - considered equally important by Skills4EOSC, these are not specific to the occupation or sector.

- **Communication**
- **Conflict management/mediation** (with a patient, empathic approach)
- **Critical and analytical thinking**
- **Stakeholder engagement and networking** to translate and bridge needs
- **Creativity, curiosity, and openness** (willingness to learn)
- **Team management and project management** (results-oriented planning and organising)

Background assumptions

Main activities - Coordinator role

- Contributes to Open Science policy development by engaging with (inter)national policy-making, bringing the cross-disciplinary expertise needed for local policy development, implementation, and monitoring.
- Understands research stakeholder needs and contributes to developing, implementing, and monitoring institutional RDM policy and Data Governance, along with tools and services to support these. Promotes and communicates the importance of Open Science and FAIR to all levels within the organization (e.g., policy makers, senior management, researchers, postgraduates, etc.).
- Analyses trends in data management infrastructure, tools, and methods that potentially improve the organisation's implementation of FAIR and CARE principles to enhance support for decision-making on Open Science. Advises on (meta)data standards and contextual documentation for data archiving.

Main activities - Embedded role

- Develops Data Management Plans templates tailored for research teams and supports researchers in writing a DMP according to the relevant template. Includes provision for post-project archiving and FAIR sharing (standards, metadata, licensing, repository selection).
- Supports researchers in good practice on data and/or software/code when writing applications to funders, implements this good practice as a regular aspect of doing research, and liaises with (technical) RDM experts inside and outside the institute to adopt effective solutions to challenges.
- Advises and supports researchers on data-infrastructure and tools, and adoption of innovative techniques or tools, including those provided by relevant (inter)national data-infrastructure and tools.
- Identifies gaps and takes action if needed to ensure ethical conduct and awareness of the potential impacts of data reuse, management, and sharing

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monitors RDM skills of researchers and research support staff in the institute and refers researchers to RDM related facilities and services. • Develops and delivers training tailored to learners' needs, aligned with wider institutional policies and plans. • Maintains networks of RDM and research support related colleagues. 	<p>on wider society.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advises on the use of disciplinary standards and ontologies, and relevant community practices that are applied in producing FAIR research outputs. • Supports researchers on legal and regulatory compliance aligning local practices with ethical conduct through connections with the institutional privacy officers, legal advisers, and research ethics bodies. • Provides ongoing support and guidance to researchers in following best practices for data management, ensuring ethical considerations and compliance are met. • Encourages collaboration across departments and institutions to share knowledge and improve research data management practices.
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Contributes to which Open Science outcomes?

- Digital research objects are as FAIR and open as possible and as closed as necessary.
- Opportunities are identified for creating or connecting with professional Open Science networks at institutional, cross-institutional, regional, national, or international levels.
- Relevant competence centres with a FAIR data and Open Science support role are utilised effectively according to local needs and policies.
- Open Science skills and practices are facilitated and enhanced using, where appropriate, EOSC resources and services, including any relevant Open Educational Resources.
- Research data and other digital objects are effectively managed to ensure their suitability for archiving and sharing, and advancement of research methods appropriate to the discipline(s).

Further information

Contributors: Nida van Leersum, Päivi Rauste, Bojana Koteska, Laurence Horton, Karsten Kryger Hansen, Angus Whyte

Open Science Skills Terms

OS skills terms match the essential skills in this MVS to competence definitions from relevant taxonomies. The selected terms offer further information to help identify the learning objectives for skills development. Sources: European Skills, Competences and Occupations ontology ([ESCO](#)), [ResearchComp](#), [terms4FAIRskills](#), [Center Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement](#).

ESCO Research Skills: [Demonstrate disciplinary expertise](#); [Manage findable accessible interoperable and reusable data](#); [Apply research ethics and scientific integrity principles in research activities](#); [Increase the impact of science on policy and society](#); [Interact professionally in research and professional environments](#).

ESCO Transversal Skills: [Negotiate compromises](#); [Think critically](#); [Think analytically](#); [Advise others](#); [Demonstrate curiosity](#); [Adapt to change](#); [Lead others](#); [Work in teams](#); [Meet commitments](#); [Organise information, objects and resources](#).

ResearchComp: Develop networks; Teach in academic or vocational contexts; Promote open innovation; Promote the transfer of knowledge; Build mentor-mentee relationships.

Terms4FAIRskills: [Data policy](#); [knowledge to contextualise fair principles to domain](#); [Service level management](#); [Data curation](#); [Preservation](#); [Open access publishing](#); [Data access risk assessment and mitigation](#); [Information security](#); [Securing sustainable funding](#); [Software preservation](#); [Metadata exposure](#).

CSCCE: [Consultation and listening](#); [Advocacy](#); [Landscape analysis](#).

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Scholtens, S., Jetten, M., Böhmer, J., Staiger, C., Slouwerhof, I., Van Der Geest, M., & Van Gelder, C. W. G. (2022). *Final report: Towards FAIR data steward as profession for the lifesciences. Report of a ZonMw funded collaborative approach built on existing expertise (Version 4)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.3471707>

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Digital Collections Curator

V1.1 2025

DOCUMENT LOG

Issue	Date	Comment	Author
0.1	09/04/2024	Initial content based on Data Steward MVS and curation skills workshop	Nikos Gänsdorfer, Angus Whyte, Clara Linés
0.2	20/05/2024	Comments	Angus Whyte, Clara Linés
0.3	10/06/2024	Additional references	Angus Whyte
0.4	30/07/2024	Updated list of skills	Clara Linés, Angus Whyte
0.5	1/08/2024	Edited soft skills using terms from ESCO ontology	Angus Whyte
0.6	5/08/2024	Edited to align with learning objectives	Clara Linés, Angus Whyte
0.7	27/08/2024	Minor edits	Angus Whyte
0.8	29/08/2024	Annotated with terms from ESCO etc.	Angus Whyte
0.9	1/10/ 2024	Minor changes from reflection on training pilot	Angus Whyte
1.0	19/11/2024	Restructured to conform to new template	Angus Whyte
1.1	17/06/2025	Removed non-essential terms	Claire Sowinski, Angus Whyte

Introduction: Open Science mission for this role

The Minimum Viable Skillset (MVS) offers a framework for describing and recognising activities and skills required for open science specialists. This MVS, for Digital Collections Curators working in GLAM institutions (galleries, libraries, archives, and museums), describes expertise required to enhance the value of digital collections, e.g. to the scholarly community and the public, while respecting rights and legitimate interests of all other stakeholders. This includes individuals or groups described by collections, researchers wishing to use them, as well as host institutions and other organisations involved in maintaining access (e.g. infrastructures, funders).

A Digital Collections Curator supports digitisation and works with others to ensure the long-term preservation and reusability of data derived from collections. They advise and train researchers and other GLAM staff on policy, guidelines, data management plans, institutional infrastructure, and data management tools relevant to the domains that are the focus of digital collections in their institution. They provide support in planning and implementing principles for FAIR digital objects and for decolonisation of collections, using these principles to shape data sharing practices.

Expertise in digital collections curation is usually distributed among several people, drawing on internal skills and external services provided to the GLAM institution, e.g. by a Competence Centre or other provider. The appropriate distribution of expertise depends on cost and the availability of skills to meet needs. The document includes background assumptions about contextual factors that may influence these.

Digital Collections Curators play a key role in the EOSC. As practitioners and advocates of Open Science, and as educators and enablers of others, they are likely to be both consumers and providers of services or resources.

Digital Collections Curator

A Digital Collections Curator works with stakeholders to establish and manage processes to generate and maintain digital data collections with their associated metadata. They also make collections usable for research, facilitate their quality assurance, and their transformation into research outputs. The role also supports informed decisions about the openness of collections and data derived from them, for re-use in line with ethical, legal and social expectations.

Associated function titles: Various other job titles are relevant to the role described here, e.g. Data Curator, Data Steward, or Data Manager.

Organisational context

Digital Collection Curators serve research teams and departments in institutions that are directly involved in the publication of collection objects or the production of research results, such as:

- Museums that conduct research
- Libraries and archives
- University collections
- Research infrastructures

Essential skills for this role

Each requires understanding of the context, the processes required to perform the main activities involved, and transversal competences (“soft skills”) to engage with the various stakeholders.

- **Knowledge of principles** relating to FAIR data, Open Science, and Open Collections, the policy and legal contexts to these principles, and strategies for implementing them in diverse GLAM institutions and domains. This includes understanding of training requirements to build the essential skills for Open Collections practices, policies and procedures, including knowledge/awareness of relevant software development.
- **Knowledge and understanding of practical steps to manage Collections as Data**, to apply Open Science principles to data derived from digital collections. This includes abilities to establish and maintain good data management practices relevant to open digital collections, and to ensure data quality and long-term preservation by performing data transformation and migration, establishing processes for information security, risk management, version control, and documentation of provenance and contextual metadata about digital objects. It also includes the ability to promote the value of good data management among data producers and users, researchers, support services colleagues, and relevant committees.
- **Ability to apply FAIR principles** to collections, and to other digital objects they interoperate with, including software. This includes the capability to apply standards, ontologies, infrastructure and tools for (meta)data publishing and sharing, and for managing the associated workflows. It also includes the capability to provide open access to collections.

- **Ability to establish governance processes** to handle ethical and legal/ regulatory aspects of managing digital open collections in the GLAM sector. This requires understanding of processes to handle intellectual property rights, deal with personal data, and ensure the responsible reuse of digital objects, including through the decolonisation of collections. It also requires familiarity with sustainable business modelling approaches relevant to the sector, including appropriate levels of resource pooling and service coordination.

Soft / transversal skills - considered equally important by Skills4EOSC, these are not specific to the occupation or sector.

- **Ability to interact positively and productively with others**, e.g.when addressing audiences, moderating discussions, or collaborating in teams and networks. This includes abilities to effect agreements, reconcile, resolve problems, and provide improvement strategies with a patient, empathetic approach.
- **Exercise critical judgement**, develop own assumptions, and establish a way of working based on critical thinking.
- **Ability to develop innovative, novel solutions**, with curiosity, openness, and a willingness to learn. This includes abilities to obtain and synthesize information to identify and explore trends, opportunities, threats (also based on intuition and creativity); and to identify alternative paths to turn ideas into action, selecting the most appropriate approach.
- **Direct activities and tasks**, establish schedules and coordinate the activities of groups and individuals to complete objectives on time and within budget.

Background assumptions

Main activities of the Digital Collections Curator

- **Identify the needs of stakeholders and contributes to the development, implementation and monitoring of institutional policies** governing research data derived from collections, together with related tools and services to support them, including through contribution to (inter)national policy development.
- **Promote and communicate** the importance of Open Collections, FAIR and decolonisation principles at all levels within the museum or collection.
- **Monitor the capabilities of researchers** to reuse open collections responsibly, and analyse trends in tools and methods that could improve the implementation of FAIR and CARE principles to support responsible reuse, providing advice on the use of disciplinary standards and ontologies to produce FAIR research outputs, and relevant (meta)data standards and contextual documentation to archive data for future reuse.
- **Support researchers and other users of collections to apply best practices** in managing data and digital objects in relevant domains, including when preparing proposals to funders, and implement these best practices in collaboration with RDM experts and stakeholders to find effective solutions to challenges.
- Advise and support researchers who use GLAM collections on **adopting relevant data infrastructures, innovative techniques and tools** to support them, including those

provided by relevant (inter)national data infrastructures and tools.

- Assist researchers using GLAM collections to **comply with laws, regulations, and policies on legal and ethical behaviour**, through liaison with institutional data protection officers, legal experts, and research ethics bodies. As a result, identify gaps and take action where needed to ensure ethical behaviour and awareness of the potential impact of data reuse, management and sharing on society.
- **Maintain networks** of colleagues involved in research data management and research support in the GLAM sector, including by co-developing and delivering training tailored to the needs of collection users and stakeholders, and by collaborating to deliver overall institutional policies and plans.

Contributes to which Open Science outcomes?

- Digital collection objects are as FAIR and open as possible and as closed as necessary.
- Opportunities for the creation of or connection to professional Open Collections networks at institutional, cross-institutional, regional, national or international level are identified.
- Relevant competence centres with a FAIR Data and Open Collections support function are effectively used according to local needs and strategies.
- Open Collections skills and practices are promoted and enhanced through the use of EOSC resources and services, including relevant Open Educational Resources (OER), where appropriate.
- Collection data, metadata and related digital objects are effectively managed to ensure their suitability for archiving and sharing, and the further development of research methods appropriate to the discipline(s).

Further Information

Contributors: Nikos Gänsdorfer, Angus Whyte, Clara Linés

Open Science skills terms

OS skills terms match the essential skills in this MVS to competence definitions from relevant taxonomies. The selected terms offer further information to help identify the learning objectives for skills development. Sources: European Skills, Competences and Occupations ontology ([ESCO](#)), [ResearchComp](#), [terms4FAIRskills](#), [Center Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement](#).

ESCO Research Skills: [Demonstrate disciplinary expertise](#); [Manage findable accessible interoperable and reusable data](#); [Manage intellectual property rights](#); [Apply research ethics and scientific integrity principles in research activities](#); [Operate open-source software](#); [Increase the impact of science on policy and society](#); [Interact professionally in research and professional environments](#).

ESCO Transversal Skills: [Negotiate compromises](#); [Respect the diversity of cultural values and norms](#); [Think critically](#); [Think analytically](#); [Advise others](#); [Participate actively in civic life](#); [Demonstrate curiosity](#); [Approach challenges positively](#); [Adapt to change](#); [Lead others](#); [Work in](#)

[teams](#); [Meet commitments](#); [Organise information, objects and resources](#).

ResearchComp: Manage research data; Develop networks; Teach in academic or vocational contexts; Promote open innovation; Promote the transfer of knowledge; Build mentor-mentee relationships.

Terms4FAIRskills: [Data policy](#); [knowledge to contextualise fair principles to domain](#); [Service level management](#); [Data curation](#); [Preservation](#); [Open access publishing](#); [Data access risk assessment and mitigation](#); [Information security](#); [Securing sustainable funding](#); [Software preservation](#); [Metadata exposure](#).

CSCCE: [Consultation and listening](#); [Advocacy](#); [Landscape analysis](#).

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Ethics advisor

V0.4 2025

DOCUMENT LOG

Issue	Date	Comment	Author
0.1		Initial content	Luca Schirru, Valentina Colcelli, Sabrina Brizioli, Sara Casati
0.2		Draft for discussion	Above + Thomas Margoni, Angus Whyte, Laurence Horton, Dominique Green, Karolina Dostatnia, Emma Lazzeri
0.3	24/10/2024	Restructured to revised template, with ESCO terms	Bojana Koteska
0.4	17/06/2025	Alignment with survey texts Removed non-essential terms	Claire Sowinski, Angus Whyte

Introduction: Open Science mission for this role

The Minimum Viable Skillset (MVS) for Ethics Advisors focuses on the critical competencies required by professionals responsible for upholding ethical standards within Open Science. Ethics Advisors play a vital role in ensuring that research practices align with ethical principles while promoting openness, transparency, and adherence to the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable). These professionals are often tasked with balancing ethical considerations with the objectives of Open Science, including data sharing, collaboration, and accessibility, while mitigating risks related to societal, legal, and moral responsibilities.

The term "Ethics Advisor" includes professionals such as Data Ethicists, Ethics Officers, and members of Ethics Committees. These roles may vary across research institutions and projects, but all share the responsibility of ensuring that ethical guidelines are met. Ethics Advisors provide guidance on a range of issues, including research involving AI systems, dual-use technologies, animal experimentation, and broader societal impacts. They help anticipate and address potential ethical dilemmas, ensuring that research activities respect fundamental values such as accountability, transparency, inclusivity, and respect for diversity.

A key responsibility of Ethics Advisors is promoting ethical decision-making in research, while fostering a culture of openness. This includes navigating the ethical challenges posed by data protection, privacy, and the responsible use of research data. Ethics Advisors work closely with researchers, Legal Experts, and Data Protection Officers (DPOs) to create environments where ethical principles and legal compliance coexist. They provide critical input on ethical reviews, draft policies, and offer advice on complex issues such as dual-use technologies and the societal implications of scientific advancements.

In their work, Ethics Advisors promote Openness, FAIRness, and the ethical principles of responsibility/accountability, transparency, pluralism, and respect/inclusion in the realization of

Open Science within the context of research projects and organizations. Their mission is to promote accountability, transparency, and inclusivity in research, while also safeguarding against ethical risks.

Ethics advisor

Ethics Advisors play a critical role in ensuring that research practices, particularly in the context of Open Science, align with ethical standards and principles. Their primary responsibility is to promote ethical decision-making and compliance with ethical guidelines while addressing issues such as privacy, data protection, and societal impacts. Ethics Advisors navigate ethical complexities, particularly in areas involving sensitive data, AI systems, and dual-use technologies, while fostering openness and accountability. Their expertise is essential in balancing the ethical obligations required to safeguard research participants and broader societal interests, while also promoting openness and compliance with the FAIR principles.

Associated function titles: Ethics Officer, Data Protection Officer, Data Ethicist, Ethics Expert, Members of Ethics Committees.

Essential Skills for this Role

- Good understanding of OS and its practices.
- Ability to establish the appropriate strategy, frameworks and course of actions to foster and enhance OS.
- Expert knowledge of the FAIR principles and how to apply them (e.g. publishing research data in a way that is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable).
- Ability to identify ethical issues, raise awareness and apply the necessary measures to address the existing and applicable ethical principles (eg transparency and accountability), frameworks (e.g. RRI Framework) and codes of conduct, including but not limited to the ones concerning research (e.g. European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity -- ALLEA and the OECD's Best Practices for Ensuring Scientific Integrity and Preventing Misconduct).
- Ability to identify and address ethical issues related to personal data governance during all the data lifecycle, including but not limited to the management of personal data (e.g. collecting, storing and sharing), development and management of related policies, and knowledge of the applicable regulations on privacy and personal data protection that may concern to ethical aspects.
- Ability to raise awareness and provide instructions on (research) data ethics, and whenever needed, on specific scenarios and fields of research (e.g. in case of using data-driven technologies, this may include an expert knowledge on the rules provided in the Artificial Intelligence Act and related regulations and knowledge of best practices related to avoiding bias in data processing).
- Ability to establish connections and ease communication between different players (e.g. researchers) and bodies (e.g. legal department and the research ethics committees) when addressing ethical issues.
- Knowledge of the necessary resources to raise awareness and advise on the ethical use and management of intellectual property rights and non-personal data
-

Soft / Transversal Skills - considered equally important by Skills4EOSC, these are not specific to the occupation or sector.

- Leadership
- Effective communication
- Stakeholder engagement and networking
- Management skills
- Critical and Analytical thinking
- Collaboration
- Sharing knowledge and processes

Background assumptions

Main activities

- Map and identify ethical concerns inside the organization/ research project.
- Advise the organization on the compatibility of local practices with ethical principles and the existing frameworks and codes of conduct (eg FAIR, CARE principles, the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, RRI framework).
- Advocate for pluralism and inclusion in Open Science.
- Set up policies, guidelines and other instruments necessary to the realization of the ethical principles concerning OS.
- Interact with stakeholders in order to ensure that research is being conducted in a responsible and transparent manner, and that consider all stakeholders rights and interests.

Contributes to which Open Science outcomes?

- Raised awareness of the ethical principles in open research through the interaction with stakeholders, and advocacy activities.
- Main ethical issues are addressed in the practice of Open Science in the relevant context e.g. the organization or research project.

Further information

Contributors: Luca Schirru, Valentina Colcelli, Sabrina Brizioli, Sara Casati, Thomas Margoni, Angus Whyte, Laurence Horton, Dominique Green, Karolina Dostatnia, Emma Lazzeri, Bojana Koteska

Open Science skills terms

OS skills terms match the essential skills in this MVS to competence definitions from relevant taxonomies. The selected terms offer further information to help identify the learning objectives for skills development. Sources: European Skills, Competences and Occupations ontology ([ESCO](#)), [ResearchComp](#), [terms4FAIRskills](#), [Center Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement](#).

ESCO Research Skills: [Apply research ethics and scientific integrity principles in research activities](#); [Demonstrate disciplinary expertise](#); [Interact professionally in research and professional environments](#); [Manage intellectual property rights](#); [Perform project management](#); [Promote the transfer of knowledge](#).

ESCO Transversal Skills: [Solve problems](#); [Identify problems](#); [Show initiative](#); [Respect confidentiality obligations](#); [Comply with regulations](#); [Demonstrate trustworthiness](#); [Moderate a discussion](#); [Address an audience](#); [Advise others](#); [Motivate others](#); [Assume responsibility](#); [Plan](#); [Time management](#); [Resolve conflicts](#); [Negotiate compromises](#); [Demonstrate intercultural competence](#); [Think creatively](#); [Manage time](#); [Think critically](#); [Think analytically](#).

ResearchComp: Strategic thinking; Systemic thinking; Interact professionally.

Terms4FAIRskills: [Data policy](#); [Ethical application of patents, licenses](#); [Research governance](#); [Data-driven decision management](#); [Information security](#); [Resource management](#).

CSCCE: [Strategy development](#); [Media relations](#); [Speaking and presenting](#); [Consultation and listening](#); [Meeting facilitation](#); [Engagement](#); [Record-keeping](#); [Advocacy](#); [Collaboration](#); [Knowledge brokering](#).

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[content/uploads/dlm_uploads/2019/03/SPARCEurope_ResearchIntegrityBrief.pdf](https://sparceurope.org/wp-content/uploads/dlm_uploads/2019/03/SPARCEurope_ResearchIntegrityBrief.pdf)

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Demchenko, Y., Belloum, A., and Wiktorski, T. *EDISON Data Science Framework: Part 1. Data Science Competence Framework (CF-DS) Release 2. Item 4.6.2, Table 4.6. The 21st Century workplace skills*. p.30.

Knowledge Broker

V0.3 2025

DOCUMENT LOG

Issue	Date	Comment	Author
0.1	June 2023	Final draft for D2.1	Emma Lazzeri, Sara di Giorgio, Dominique Green, Claire Sowinski, Gabriela Torres Ramos, Betty Evangelinou, Bojana Koteska
0.2	October 2024	Restructured to add ESCO terms and highlight essential skills	Bojana Koteska
0.3	June 2025	Alignment with survey texts Removed non-essential terms	Claire Sowinski, Angus Whyte

Introduction: Open Science mission for this role

Knowledge brokers serve as vital intermediaries in the transfer of knowledge between experts and stakeholders. They are responsible for facilitating the dissemination of scientific information, ensuring that research findings are accessible and actionable for various audiences. Knowledge brokers promote transparency and collaboration, particularly in the context of Open Science, by bridging the gap between research and practice, enabling informed decision-making. They strive to provide unbiased and reliable information, fostering trust among stakeholders while adhering to ethical standards in knowledge sharing.

The Minimum Viable Skillset (MVS) recognises the competencies essential for individuals or teams acting as intermediaries in the knowledge transfer process. The term "knowledge broker" refers to individuals or teams who, in a variety of contexts, facilitate the transfer of knowledge from experts to a wider audience. This practice encompasses diverse use cases with the common objective of disseminating scientific information and facilitating its use in society. Typical scenarios include appointed individual experts or expert groups informing public authorities or agencies about scientific findings, as well as aggregating research data to provide an overview of specific phenomena or fields. Such efforts support evidence-based decision-making and provide trustworthy and understandable information to laypeople.

Knowledge brokers typically use their expertise to connect stakeholders with the information and resources they need to make informed decisions. They fill the gaps between science and various stakeholders, including policymakers, practitioners, and the public. Sometimes, groups, such as committees or learned societies, undertake this role.

A notable subtype within this field is the "honest broker." An honest broker serves as an impartial mediator, facilitating communication and decision-making among individuals or groups with differing interests or values. They maintain neutrality and bias-free positions, providing all parties with accurate information to help negotiate and find common ground. This role is especially critical in situations requiring fair and transparent processes, such as conflict resolution or public policy development.

Knowledge brokers operate within various organizational contexts, including ministries, governmental organizations, research-performing organizations, national agencies, national funding organizations, communication/media agencies, and committees or learned societies.

In relation to Open Science, the knowledge broker plays a crucial role in bridging the gap between research and practice by connecting researchers with stakeholders who can benefit from their work. They help create a more open, transparent, and collaborative research environment, leading to more effective and impactful research outcomes. This may involve collaborating closely with researchers to translate findings into actionable recommendations or providing policymakers with access to the latest accessible scientific evidence to inform decision-making. Additionally, knowledge brokers may promote Open Science practices within their organizations or communities, advocating for open access publishing, developing data-sharing policies, and supporting dissemination of research findings to a wider audience.

Knowledge broker

Associated function titles: Knowledge Broker, Honest Broker, Research Liaison, Information Specialist, Policy Advisor, Evidence Synthesis Expert, Science Communicator, Stakeholder Engagement Coordinator.

Essential Skills for this Role

- Familiarity with policy making practices and procedures.
- Understanding of open, ethical and responsible research principles.
- Managing considerable amount of information related to OS practices.
- Searching, retrieving, appraising and synthesizing evidence.
- Developing and maintaining network of researchers, policymakers, and other stakeholders to help the promotion and implementation of OS practices and support for co-creation activities.
- Providing training and education to researchers, policymakers, and public citizens about OS practices.
- Evaluating research findings and identifying potential conflicts of interest.
- Tailoring resources to local needs and assessing the implementation context.

Soft / Transversal Skills - considered equally important by Skills4EOSC, these are not specific to the occupation or sector.

- Communication
- Collaboration
- Leadership
- Self-confidence
- Citizens and stakeholders engagement

- Influencing
- Negotiation and diplomacy
- Problem-solving
- Innovative thinking
- Analytical and research skills
- Adaptability to changes
- Stakeholder management and influencing
- Facilitation

Background assumptions

Main activities

- Bridging the interface between science and policy by ensuring mutual understanding among these parties.
- Aligning the needs of the policy community with the evidence synthesis provided.
- Ensuring that the policy community have a good understanding of the implications of the evidence proffered.
- Ensuring the quality and transparency of evidence synthesis.
- Ensuring the evidence synthesis has appropriate expert inputs.
- Identifying options and providing advice from a scientific viewpoint.
- Identifying constraints, uncertainties and caveats.
- Contextualising the FAIR and OS principles to specific domains.
- Identifying strengths and weaknesses in how OS is applied.
- Identifying needs for change in OS policy or practice in relevant research domains.
- Ensuring all actors are engaged in co-creation actions.

Contributes to which Open Science outcomes?

- Information needs of referenced stakeholders/interlocutors are identified and addressed, by bridging specialised scientific data and information and facilitating the stakeholders' understanding and correct interpretation of this information.
- Concrete policy options are drafted through analysis and evaluation that is based as much as possible on co-creation, continuous knowledge exchange and capacity building.
- Knowledge producers and users are facilitated in an objective and transparent manner, by translating science into accessible and policy-usable knowledge.
- Open Science and FAIR principles are applied in the knowledge production chain to enhance the uptake into public policy of scientifically developed knowledge.

- Policymakers are helped to identify options, and understand the likely impact of choices, by providing advice from a scientific viewpoint.
- Researchers are helped to understand the potential impact on policy makers of their outcomes.
- Through advocacy, FAIR and Open Science principles become related to the organisation's local policies and processes including its research practices and goals.

Further information

Contributors: Emma Lazzeri, Sara di Giorgio, Dominique Green, Claire Sowinski, Gabriela Torres Ramos, Betty Evangelinou, Bojana Koteska

Open Science skills terms

OS skills terms match the essential skills in this MVS to competence definitions from relevant taxonomies. The selected terms offer further information to help identify the learning objectives for skills development. Sources: European Skills, Competences and Occupations ontology ([ESCO](#)), [ResearchComp](#), [terms4FAIRskills](#), [Center Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement](#).

ESCO Research Skills: [Increase the impact of science on policy and society](#); [Apply research ethics and scientific integrity principles in research activities](#); [Demonstrate disciplinary expertise](#); [Synthesise information](#); [Develop professional network with researchers and scientists](#); [Promote the transfer of knowledge](#); [Promote the participation of citizens in scientific and research activities](#); [Mentor individuals](#); [Teach in academic or vocational contexts](#); [Evaluate research activities](#); [Manage intellectual property rights](#); [Interact professionally in research and professional environments](#).

ESCO Transversal Skills: [Organise information, objects and resources](#); [Demonstrate curiosity](#); [Conduct web searches](#); [Critically evaluate information and its sources](#); [Moderate a discussion](#); [Communicate with a non-scientific audience](#); [Demonstrate intercultural competence](#); [Demonstrate trustworthiness](#); [Make decisions](#); [Motivate others](#); [Show confidence](#); [Plan](#); [Resolve conflicts](#); [Show empathy](#); [Negotiate compromises](#); [Promote ideas, products, services](#); [Respect the diversity of cultural values and norms](#); [Manage time](#).

ResearchComp: Promote citizen science; Mobilise resources.

Terms4FAIRskills: [Data policy](#); [Ethical application of patents, licenses](#); [Information security](#); [Open access publishing](#); [Open peer review](#); [Open innovation](#); [Research integrity, attribution, impact awareness](#); [Research governance](#); [Assessment on FAIR data criteria](#); [Training in open and fair methods](#).

CSCCE: [Consultation and listening](#); [Data analysis](#); [Landscape analysis](#); [Advocacy](#); [Collaboration](#); [Knowledge brokering](#); [Engagement](#); [Moderation, mediation and intervention](#); [Speaking and presenting](#); [Evaluation and assessment](#); [Cultural competence](#); [Meeting facilitation](#); [Record-keeping](#); [Operational planning and implementation](#); [Social media](#); [Content planning](#).

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Legal expert

V0.4 2025

DOCUMENT LOG

Issue	Date	Comment	Author
0.1		Initial content	Luca Schirru, Valentina Colcelli, Sabrina Brizioli, Sara Casati
0.2		Draft for discussion	Above + Thomas Margoni, Angus Whyte, Laurence Horton, Dominique Green, Karolina Dostatnia, Emma Lazzeri
0.3			
0.4	17/06/2025	Alignment with survey texts Removed non-essential terms	Claire Sowinski, Angus Whyte

Introduction: Open Science mission for this role

The Minimum Viable Skillset (MVS) for legal experts provides a structured understanding of the critical competencies required by professionals responsible for ensuring legal compliance within Open Science. These individuals play a key role in managing the complex legal landscapes surrounding both personal and non-personal data, safeguarding the rights of third parties while promoting openness and adherence to the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable). Legal experts must navigate the tension between the existing property-based legal framework and the openness essential to achieving Open Science objectives, particularly in areas such as Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) and data protection.

The term "Legal Expert" encompasses a variety of professionals, including Legal Consultants, Lawyers, Regulatory Affairs Managers, Data Protection Officers (DPOs), and Technology Transfer/IP Lawyers. Each role has varying degrees of legal authority, with some professionals, such as Regulatory Affairs Managers, not always licensed to provide legal advice yet having significant expertise in legal matters. A key aspect of this role is ensuring compliance with regulations such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), while also facilitating open access to research materials, data reuse, and collaboration. Legal experts also assist in aligning organizations with legal standards, mitigating risks related to privacy, intellectual property, and contractual obligations.

An important responsibility of legal experts is bridging the gap between the goals of Open Science and regulatory requirements. They work closely with researchers and institutions to ensure that the use of protected materials and sensitive data complies with existing laws, while promoting openness and facilitating the lawful sharing and reuse of scientific information. Their work often includes drafting agreements, managing licensing, ensuring the preservation of protected materials, and advising on data-sharing practices.

The mission of a legal expert in Open Science is to promote openness and FAIRness in a legal system predominantly centred on exclusive property rights, while simultaneously mitigating legal risks

through a proactive approach to compliance with personal and non-personal data regulations. In doing so, they contribute significantly to building a transparent and accessible research environment, which is critical for the advancement of Open Science.

Legal expert

Legal experts play a critical role in ensuring that research practices, particularly in the context of Open Science, comply with complex legal frameworks. Their primary responsibility is to safeguard the rights of third parties by ensuring adherence to national, regional, and international regulations governing both personal and non-personal data. Legal experts manage the tension between traditional intellectual property laws, which are often based on exclusive ownership, and the openness required to advance Open Science goals. Their expertise is essential in mitigating legal risks, ensuring data protection, and promoting openness and compliance with FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable).

Associated function titles: Legal Consultant, Lawyer, Regulatory Affairs Manager, Technology Transfer/IP Lawyer, Data Protection Officer, Legal Advisor.

Essential Skills for this Role

- Good understanding of OS and its practices.
- Ability to establish the appropriate strategy, frameworks and course of actions to foster and enhance OS.
- Expert knowledge of the FAIR principles and how to apply them, especially the one concerning (re)usability e.g. copyright licensing rules and existing frameworks like the Creative Commons licenses.
- Ability to identify ethical issues and apply the necessary measures to address the existing and applicable ethical principles, frameworks and codes of conduct, including but not limited to the ones concerning research, e.g. the RRI Framework and the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (ALLEA).
- Ability to address legal issues related to personal data governance, including but not limited to the management of personal data; development and management of policies on privacy and data protection, e.g. consent forms, data policies, etc; and expert knowledge on the application of regulations concerning privacy and personal data protection.
- Ability to develop, negotiate and assess data use agreements, based on expert knowledge of the regulations that commonly govern these documents.

Soft / Transversal Skills - considered equally important by Skills4EOSC, these are not specific to the occupation or sector.

- Problem-solving
- Effective communication
- Critical and Analytical thinking
- Collaboration
- Translating needs/bridging function

- Research skills
- Flexibility and adaptability
- Proactiveness and responsiveness

Background assumptions

Main activities

- Promotes and supports Open Access and other Open Science related legal and ethical principles.
- Monitors the regulatory landscape and national policies concerning OS e.g. GDPR, ODD, DGA, Data Act proposal, IPR-related directives and regulations.
- Assesses and addresses legal risks concerning Intellectual Property Rights, e.g., Personal and Non-Personal Data Protection and Governance, Licensing and Information Security.
- Promotes Open Science by employing available instruments e.g. licensing frameworks, rights retention strategies; and normative tools e.g. copyright exceptions and limitations.
- Develops policies, contracts and other instruments needed to put into action the legal rules and ethical principles concerning OS.
- Advises the organisation about the compatibility of local practices with current legal frameworks.

Contributes to which Open Science outcomes?

- The organisation is able to adopt existing licensing frameworks e.g. Creative Commons, and enjoys the free uses allowed under the existing legal framework e.g. copyright limitations and exceptions.
- The organisation is equipped with policies, contracts and other instruments needed to apply the legal rules and ethical principles concerning Open Science.

Further information

Contributors: Luca Schirru, Valentina Colcelli, Sabrina Brizioli, Sara Casati, Thomas Margoni, Angus Whyte, Laurence Horton, Dominique Green, Karolina Dostatnia, Emma Lazzeri

Open Science skills terms

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ESCO Research Skills: [Manage Intellectual Property Rights](#); [Apply Research Ethics and Scientific Integrity Principles in Research Activities](#); [Manage Open Publications](#).

ESCO Transversal Skills: [Solve Problems](#); [Identify Problems](#); [Show Initiative](#); [Comply with Regulations](#); [Negotiate Compromises](#); [Resolve Conflicts](#); [Organise Information, Objects and Resources](#); [Moderate a Discussion](#); [Think Critically](#); [Think Analytically](#); [Build](#)

Networks; Demonstrate Intercultural Competence; Demonstrate Trustworthiness; Think Quickly; Demonstrate Willingness to Learn; Attend to Detail; Demonstrate Curiosity.

ResearchComp: Strategic thinking; Systemic thinking; Analytical thinking; Cope with pressure; Plan self-organisation.

Terms4FAIRskills: Assessment on FAIR data criteria; Knowledge to contextualise FAIR principles to domain; Information security; Data policy; Ethical application of patents, licenses; Data access risk assessment and mitigation; Data driven decision management; Research integrity, attribution, impact awareness; Research governance; Change management.

CSCCE: Strategy development; Content planning; Operational planning and implementation; Speaking and presenting; Consultation and listening; Collaboration.

Reference sources

Whyte, A. & Ashley, K. (2017). *Deliverable D7.1: Skills landscape analysis and competence model*. EOSCPilot. Annex A. *Indicative Scope of data stewardship competences and their mapping to other frameworks*. pp. 60-63 (mentioning other sources, like the EDISON Data Science Competence Framework, RDA Interest Group Educ. & Training in Data Handling (Wiki), and Purdue University/SAPP Nelson – Data Information Literacy, which also contributed to these skills).

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Demchenko, Y., Belloum, A., and Wiktorski, T., *EDISON Data Science Framework: Part 1. Data Science Competence Framework (CF-DS) Release 2*. Item 4.6.2, Table 4.6. The 21st Century workplace skills. p.30.

Policy maker – Evidence-based policy

V0.7 2025

DOCUMENT LOG

Issue	Date	Comment	Author
0.1	09/12/2022	Initial content	Arnaud Gingold, Karla Avanço, Gabriela Torres-Ramos, Claire Sowinski,
0.2	15/12/2022	Draft for discussion	Arnaud Gingold, Karla Avanço, Gabriela Torres-Ramos, Claire Sowinski, Angus Whyte, Dominique Green
0.3	17/01/2023	Revised to split evidence-based policy maker from OS policy maker, following discussion in WP2, WP3. Removed division of soft skills vs technical competences	Katerina Kyprianou, Ognjen Prnjat, Joy Davidson, Luca Schirru, Emma Lazzeri, Angus Whyte, Dominique Green
0.4	6/02/2023	“type 1’ and ‘type 2’ reordered to match survey questionnaire	Angus Whyte
0.5	21/10/2024	Moved essential skills to top, added ESCO terms	Bojana Koteska
0.6	27/11/2024	Soft skills edited, minor edits for length	Angus Whyte
0.7	17/06/2025	Alignment with survey texts Removed non-essential terms	Claire Sowinski, Angus Whyte

Introduction: Open Science mission for this role

The Minimum Viable Skillset (MVS) sets out to describe a shared framework for recognizing the competencies required for policymakers in advancing Open Science. Policymakers play a key role in creating the strategic conditions that promote Open Science practices and ensure their integration into national and international research frameworks. They work with stakeholders to establish, implement, and govern policies that support the adoption of Open Science, providing the necessary frameworks, resources, and partnerships that enable the transparent, collaborative, and accessible use of research data.

In the Open Science ecosystem, policymakers serve as both advocates and enablers of Open Science, ensuring that the principles of transparency, accessibility, and collaboration are embedded within research practices and governance structures. Their role is crucial in fostering the use of Open Science in evidence-based decision-making, aligning policy goals with scientific research outcomes.

The MVS for policymakers recognises two complementary but distinct roles. The first focuses on developing policies that support Open Science, described as ‘Research Policy/Decision Maker Facilitating Open Science’. The second is focused on using credible research data to inform specific policy decisions and is described as ‘Evidence-informed Policy and Decision Maker.’

Policy maker – Evidence-based policy

Evidence-informed Policy and Decision Makers gather, assess, and synthesize credible research data to design policies addressing specific societal or scientific issues. They ensure that policy decisions are data-driven and aligned with the principles of Open Science, considering the relevance and quality of evidence to inform their decisions.

Associated function titles: Policy Designer, Open Science Data Analyst, Policy Advisor.

Essential skills and competences

- Basic understanding of OS/ FAIR principles.
- Knowledge of OS services, resources and research practices that produce evidence relevant to the decision-making context.
- Expertise in applying evidence from OS to the decision-making context, considering the opportunities, limitations, and constraints.
- Knowledge management: synthesising outputs of research and consultation, identifying their relevance to specific issues and stakeholders.
- Basic knowledge of research integrity principles, frameworks and ethical codes.
- Knowledge of the responsible use of data-driven technologies.

Soft / Transversal Skills - considered equally important by Skills4EOSC, these are not specific to the occupation or sector.

- Negotiating with stakeholders to articulate rights and responsibilities for policy implementation.
- Advocating policy measures by addressing the audiences needed to mobilise key enablers and other human resources.
- Mobilising and managing financial and material resources, demonstrating trustworthiness.
- Complying with regulations and respecting confidentiality obligations.
- Using initiative to formulate policy implementation strategies.
- Applying systemic thinking to critically evaluate evidence and its sources.

Background assumptions

Main activities – Decision-maker role

- Identifies available OS outcomes relevant to an issue that requires a policy.
- Collaborates with expert communities for elicitation, review and evaluation of data and design of a policy.
- Deploys appropriate policy outcome monitoring and evaluation designs based on OS evidence.

- Ensures inclusiveness in evidence's production and evaluation.
- Promotes and supports OS as a source of evidence.

Contributes to which Open Science outcomes?

- Thorough research is carried out of available open data to identify information that is timely, relevant and credible.
- Citizens and researchers are consulted appropriately considering the specificity of their activity (scientist vs. politician) and role (honest broker vs. issue advocate).
- Gathered information is synthesised to enable design of a policy relevant to the specific issue.

Further information

Contributors: Arnaud Gingold, Karla Avanço, Gabriela Torres-Ramos, Claire Sowinski, Angus Whyte, Dominique Green, Katerina Kyprianou, Ognjen Prnjat, Joy Davidson, Luca Schirru, Emma Lazzeri, Bojana Koteska, Angus Whyte.

Open Science skills terms

OS skills terms match the essential skills in this MVS to competence definitions from relevant taxonomies. The selected terms offer further information to help identify the learning objectives for skills development. Sources: European Skills, Competences and Occupations ontology ([ESCO](#)), [ResearchComp](#), [terms4FAIRskills](#), [Center Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement](#).

ESCO Research Skills: [Increase the impact of science on policy and society](#); [Promote the transfer of knowledge](#); [Apply research ethics and scientific integrity principles in research activities](#); [Synthesise information](#); [Manage intellectual property rights](#); [Demonstrate disciplinary expertise](#).

ESCO Transversal Skills: [Exercise rights and responsibilities](#); [Manage time](#); [Plan](#); [Think critically](#); [Critically evaluate information and its sources](#); [Comply with regulations](#); [Demonstrate trustworthiness](#); [Respect confidentiality obligations](#)

ResearchComp: Mobilise resources.

Terms4FAIRskills: [Knowledge to contextualise FAIR principles to domain](#); [Resource management](#); [Data policy](#); [Data governance](#); [Privacy governance](#); [Data driven decision management](#).

CSCCE: [Operational planning and implementation](#); [Evaluation and assessment](#); [Landscape analysis](#).

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Policy maker - Research Policy

V0.7 2025

DOCUMENT LOG

Issue	Date	Comment	Author
0.1	09/12/2022	Initial content	Arnaud Gingold, Karla Avanço, Gabriela Torres-Ramos, Claire Sowinski,
0.2	15/12/2022	Draft for discussion	Arnaud Gingold, Karla Avanço, Gabriela Torres-Ramos, Claire Sowinski, Angus Whyte, Dominique Green
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0.6	27/11/2024	Soft skills edited, minor edits for length	Angus Whyte
0.7	17/06/2025	Alignment with survey texts Removed non-essential terms	Claire Sowinski, Angus Whyte

Introduction: Open Science mission for this role

The Minimum Viable Skillset (MVS) sets out to describe a shared framework for recognizing the competencies required for policymakers in advancing Open Science. Policymakers play a key role in creating the strategic conditions that promote Open Science practices and ensure their integration into national and international research frameworks. They work with stakeholders to establish, implement, and govern policies that support the adoption of Open Science, providing the necessary frameworks, resources, and partnerships that enable the transparent, collaborative, and accessible use of research data.

In the Open Science ecosystem, policymakers serve as both advocates and enablers of Open Science, ensuring that the principles of transparency, accessibility, and collaboration are embedded within research practices and governance structures. Their role is crucial in fostering the use of Open Science in evidence-based decision-making, aligning policy goals with scientific research outcomes.

The MVS for policymakers recognises two complementary but distinct roles. The first focuses on developing policies that support Open Science, described as ‘Research Policy/Decision Maker

Facilitating Open Science'. The second is focused on using credible research data to inform specific policy decisions and is described as 'Evidence-informed Policy and Decision Maker.'

Policy maker for research

Research Policy/Decision Makers act as facilitators for the development and promotion of Open Science policies. They create frameworks and provide the necessary support to promote the adoption of OS practices at national and international levels. This includes mobilizing resources, building partnerships, and ensuring policies align with OS principles like FAIR.

Associated function titles: Research Policy Maker, Science Policy Facilitator, Strategic Policy Advisor.

Essential skills and competences

- In-depth understanding of science practice, OS and FAIR principles and practices.
- Expertise in establishing appropriate strategies, frameworks and courses of action to foster and enhance OS.
- Ability to relate OS practices to the interests of Research Performing Organisations, Funders, and other stakeholders.
- Ability to assess the financial sustainability of policy outcomes.
- Knowledge about Intellectual property rights and non-personal data management.
- Knowledge of Ethical principles, frameworks and codes of conduct applicable to research.
- Knowledge of legal issues related to data governance including data use agreements and personal data regulations.

Soft / Transversal Skills - considered equally important by Skills4EOSC, these are not specific to the occupation or sector.

- Negotiating with stakeholders to articulate rights and responsibilities for policy implementation.
- Advocating policy measures by addressing the audiences needed to mobilise key enablers and other human resources.
- Mobilising and managing financial and material resources, demonstrating trustworthiness.
- Complying with regulations and respecting confidentiality obligations.
- Using initiative to formulate policy implementation strategies.
- Applying systemic thinking to critically evaluate evidence and its sources.

Background assumptions

Main activities

- Promotes and supports OS.
- Engages all the appropriate target audiences & key stakeholders.

- Identifies actions to advance policies on FAIR and OS at the relevant level (e.g. national, thematic).
- Understands the importance of addressing gaps in provision of digital skills for FAIR and OS.
- Promotes digital skills for data intensive science transferable across different sectors.
- Sets up policies or a strategic framework which serve to promote a preferred course of action and could include financial support research.

Contributes to which Open Science outcomes?

- Frameworks and incentives are established to enhance the implementation of Open Science, with the financial commitment to ensure its continuous support.
- Appropriate partnerships with key stakeholders are established.
- A team of Open Science experts is built up to inform policy implementation

Further information

Contributors: Arnaud Gingold, Karla Avanço, Gabriela Torres-Ramos, Claire Sowinski, Angus Whyte, Dominique Green, Katerina Kyprianou, Ognjen Prnjat, Joy Davidson, Luca Schirru, Emma Lazzeri, Bojana Koteska, Angus Whyte

Open Science skills terms

OS skills terms match the essential skills in this MVS to competence definitions from relevant taxonomies. The selected terms offer further information to help identify the learning objectives for skills development. Sources: European Skills, Competences and Occupations ontology ([ESCO](#)), [ResearchComp](#), [terms4FAIRskills](#), [Center Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement](#).

ESCO Research Skills: [Perform project management](#); [Show entrepreneurial spirit](#); [Promote the participation of citizens in scientific and research activities](#); [Demonstrate disciplinary expertise](#); [Increase the impact of science on policy and society](#); [Manage intellectual property rights](#); [Apply research ethics and scientific integrity principles in research activities](#); [Promote the transfer of knowledge](#); [Communicate with a non-scientific audience](#).

ESCO Transversal Skills: [Solve problems](#); [Identify problems](#); [Show initiative](#); [Plan](#); [Manage financial and material resources](#); [Comply with regulations](#); [Demonstrate trustworthiness](#); [Respect confidentiality obligations](#); [Exercise rights and responsibilities](#)

ResearchComp: Strategic thinking; Systemic thinking; Mobilise resources; Promote citizen science.

Terms4FAIRskills: [Assessment on FAIR data criteria](#); [Knowledge to contextualise FAIR principles to domain](#); [Resource management](#); [Information security](#); [Data policy](#); [Data governance](#); [Privacy governance](#).

CSCCE: [Strategy development](#); [Content planning](#); [Operational planning and implementation](#); [Engagement](#); [Advocacy](#); [Financial management](#).

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Researcher - Early Career

V0.6 2025

DOCUMENT LOG

Issue	Date	Comment	Author
0.1		Initial content	Dominique Green, Saba Sharma, Irakleitos Souyioultzoglou, Gabriela Torres-Ramos, Claire Sowinski, Karolina Dostatnia
0.2		Draft for discussion	As above
0.3		Draft for internal review	As above + Luca Schirru
0.4	8/10/2024	Added ESCO terms and updated the MVS layout	Dominique Green
0.5	16/02/2025	Response to comments by Eva Mendez	Angus Whyte
0.6	17/06/2025	Removed non-essential terms	Claire Sowinski, Angus Whyte

Introduction: Open Science mission for this role

Early career researchers for the purposes of this Minimum Viable Skillset (MVS) include PhD students, postdoctoral researchers, and other researchers within 5 to 8 years of completion of their doctorate degree. The MVS addresses the competencies and skills needed by researchers in the early stages of their research career as is related to Open OS.

A key principle of Open Science (OS) is that research is conducted openly and transparently leading to better science. Subsequently, researchers at every career stage have a key role in the promotion of Open Science and its practice. Researchers have a key role in the promotion of Open Science (OS) and its practice. Not only do early career researchers contribute to the wider uptake of skills, building their own individual skills and organizational capacities, openness is at the core of the researchers role. They are an integral part of all production and dissemination of knowledge.

OS can be facilitated via data sharing, exploring and reusing data and, data publication, and making codes available, promoting open research through peer review, and reproducible research. By adopting OS approaches, researchers work to ensure that the benefits which openness brings, such as the accessibility, reproducibility and transparency of research, are available to students, colleagues, and to society as a whole.

Early Career Researcher

Associated function titles:

- Occupations at levels R1 and R2 in the [European Framework for Research Careers](#), e.g. PhD students, Post-doctoral researchers
- Other researchers (working outside of academia and research councils)

Essential Skills for this Role

- Good understanding of OS and its practices, in a discipline-specific context, particularly knowledgeable of policies, opportunities and practices of OS (e.g., open access, data storage and archival).
- Sound knowledge of the data life cycle and adequate capacity to implement FAIR principles using discipline-specific resources.
- Ability to assess FAIRness of existing data, and to capture, process, analyse, and preserve data according to OS principles.
- Experience in using tools for conducting research, managing and sharing research output.
- Commitment to undertaking training on digital-oriented research practices.
- Research management skills: Ability to design an open research strategy, implement an open research vision, and coordinate research activities that embed open science principles.
- Entrepreneurial skills: Ability to identify and apply for OS funding opportunities; ability to acquire funding that furthers open science goals, writing grants and funding applications.
- Good understanding of legal aspects of research relevant to their field of expertise, and of relevant Open Science practices. These include, but not limited to: Intellectual Property Rights e.g. copyright, patents, and trade secrets; and other Non-Personal Data e.g. use of IoT data and research data; Personal Data Protection and Governance e.g. processing Personal Data under the current legal framework, and following existing policies on Data Protection, Privacy, (Open) Licensing rules and frameworks.
- Good understanding of ethical principles e.g. transparency, diversity, and accountability; and of best practices e.g. avoiding bias in data processing when using data-driven technologies applicable to their field of expertise. These include the general ethical principles, frameworks and codes of conduct applicable to research e.g., the RRI Framework; the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity.
- Ability to balance personal and non-personal data protection requirements with Open Science/FAIR principles.

Soft/ transversal skills - considered equally important by Skills4EOSC, these are not specific to the occupation or sector.

- Cooperation and collaboration
- Ethical orientation to open science principles and their broader social goals
- Adaptable: ability to build openness into the research process, staying up to date with research processes, software, data management systems, etc.
- Time management: incorporate Open Science/FAIR practices in a timely way during the research cycle
- Communication and interpersonal skills: engage with a variety of stakeholders
- Project management
- Presentation skills

- Critical thinking

Background assumptions

Main activities

- Promotes and supports Open Science (OS), e.g. by joining and supporting its initiatives.
- Produces research data for management, analysis, use, reuse, and dissemination.
- Collaborates with informal and formal research groups, including training students and other early career researchers on OS.
- Interacts with the general public to enhance the impact of science and research.
- Communicates research for scholarly and societal impact.
- Publishes research openly, providing metadata, data, code publicly available.

Open Science activities are apparent in all aspects of the early career researchers work flow. In conducting research, the early career researcher participates in additional activities essential to Open Science, including the following:

- Open access publishing, which can be applied to peer-reviewed journal articles, theses, book chapters, monographs, and conference papers.
- Opens data, which involves making all data that are necessary to reproduce reported results publicly accessible and digitally shareable.
- Opens materials, which includes having all components of the research methodology.

Contributes to which Open Science outcomes?

- By adopting the Open Science (OS) approach in their work, the early career researcher ensures that their research is carried out with a high degree of transparency, collegiality, and research integrity.
- By adopting OS approaches and practices, research input and outputs are shared.
- FAIR principles and methods are adopted and practiced.
- Scientific information is used more efficiently.
- The dissemination of knowledge is improved.
- Reproducibility of scientific findings is improved.

Further information

Contributors: Dominique Green, Saba Sharma, Irakleitos Souyioultzoglou, Gabriela Torres-Ramos, Claire Sowinski, Karolina Dostatnia, Luca Schirru, Angus Whyte, Eva Méndez

Open Science skills terms

OS skills terms match the essential skills in this MVS to competence definitions from relevant taxonomies. Terms are selected to add further information and to aid discovery of this MVS (an extended list is added at the foot of this document). Sources: European Skills, Competences and

Occupations ontology ([ESCO](#)), [ResearchComp](#), [terms4FAIRskills](#), [Center Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement](#).

ESCO Research Skills: [Manage open publications](#); [Operate open source software](#); [Demonstrate disciplinary expertise](#); [Manage findable accessible interoperable and reusable data](#); [Manage research data](#); [Draft scientific or academic papers and technical documentation](#); [Perform scientific research](#); [Apply for research funding](#); [Manage intellectual property rights](#); [Apply research ethics and scientific integrity principles in research activities](#); [Perform project management](#); [Communicate with a non-scientific audience](#).

ESCO Transversal Skills: [Think critically](#); [Demonstrate willingness to learn](#); [Manage financial and material resources](#); [Show entrepreneurial spirit](#); [Comply with regulation](#); [Respect confidentiality obligations](#); [Build networks](#); [Use communication and collaboration software](#); [Demonstrate intercultural competence](#); [Work in teams](#); [Demonstrate trustworthiness](#); [Show determination](#); [Adapt to change](#); [Accept criticism and guidance](#); [Demonstrate curiosity](#); [Think innovately](#); [Keep an open mind](#); [Manage time](#); [Address an audience](#); [Plan](#); [Lead others](#); [Meet commitments](#); [Organise information, objects and resources](#); [Build team spirit](#); [Show initiative](#)

ResearchComp: [Disciplinary expertise](#); [Analytical thinking](#); [Manage personal professional development](#); [Strategic thinking](#); [Systemic thinking](#); [Write research documents](#); [Develop networks](#); [Interact professionally](#); [Communicate to the broad public](#); [Disseminate results to the research community](#).

Terms4FAIRskills: [Data policy](#); [Data costs management](#); [data sharing and publication](#); [Assessment on FAIR data criteria](#); [Domain knowledge to contextualise data handling](#); [Research integrity process design](#); [Data processing](#); [Data curation](#); [Data costs management](#); [crediting research contributors](#); [data processing](#); [open peer review](#); [persistent identifiers management](#); [Data access risk assessment and mitigation](#); [Ethical application of patents, licenses](#); [Research governance](#).

CSCCE: [Strategy development](#); [Content planning](#); [Operational planning and implementation](#); [Engagement](#); [Project/programme design](#); [Collaboration](#); [Consultation and listening](#); [Speaking and presenting](#).

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(editor), Stoy, L. (editor), Publications Office, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/59065>.

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Researcher - Senior

V0.6 2025

DOCUMENT LOG

Issue	Date	Comment	Author
0.1		Initial content	Saba Sharma, Dominique Green, Irakleitos Souyioultzoglou, Gabriela Torres-Ramos, Claire Sowinski, Karolina Dostatnia
0.2		Draft for discussion	As above
0.3		Draft v3	As above + comments from Paula Martinez Lavanchy, Massimo Cocco,
0.4		Draft for internal review	As above + comments from Paula Martinez Lavanchy, Massimo Cocco, Luca Schirru
0.5	9/10/2024	Revised to add Open Science skills terms and update the MVS layout	Dominique Green
0.6	17/06/2025	Removed non-essential terms	Claire Sowinski, Angus Whyte

Introduction: Open Science mission for this role

This Skillset profile focuses on Open Science (OS) skills and activities relevant for senior researchers. Senior researchers are typically defined as those who are established within their fields, developed a level of independence, and typically lead research projects. The profile highlights the role of Senior Researchers in setting the agenda by implementing OS policies, raising awareness, and mentoring and training Early Career Researchers in the principles of Open Science.

Senior Researchers are key actors within institutional contexts in promoting Open Science and FAIR principles among research colleagues, and in supporting them ensuring that relevant data or other research outputs are made FAIR/Open in accordance with domain standards and stakeholder expectations. They are expected to be catalysts for change in how research is conducted by centring open science practices, and show leadership through implementing Open Science policies in their own research projects and teams, as well as their role in mentoring and training students, raising awareness of open science among undergraduate and masters students, and acting as a bridge between the scientific community and technical services. To achieve this mission, Senior Researchers are expected to possess an expert-level understanding of Open Science and FAIR principles and their applications in their discipline-specific contexts, including regulatory, ethical and policy requirements. In turn, they need to be supported by research organizations in this mission, in the form of Open Science policies and relevant resources to implement them.

Senior researcher

Organisational context:

- Governmental organizations
- National agencies
- National funding organizations
- Research Performing Organizations

Essential Skills for this Role

- Realise discipline-specific applications of Open Science principles and identify practices relevant to them at every stage of the research workflow.
- Outline relevant practices of Open Science and FAIR principles and create guidelines for their research teams.
- Ability to identify and track open research funding and acquire funding that furthers Open Science goals through writing grants and funding applications.
- Mentoring and training researchers and students in Open Science practices throughout the research life-cycle and nurturing professional development of Early Career Researchers in accordance with Open Science principles.
- Ability to build professional collaboration frameworks between academia and industry or other sectors to enable Open Science, build research projects that embed open science principles throughout.
- Ability to collect, annotate and document data and software, create metadata, use relevant taxonomies, handle big data sets and use existing repositories.
- Developing expert-level awareness of legal aspects related to Intellectual Property Rights e.g. copyright, patents and trade secrets; and to other Non-Personal Data e.g. IoT data and research data, Personal Data Protection and Governance e.g. processing Personal Data under the current legal framework. Managing data use agreements and policies on Data Protection, Privacy, and (Open) Licensing rules and frameworks, as well as the use of data and information which may be considered sensitive.
- Developing expert-level awareness of ethical principles e.g., transparency, diversity and accountability; and best practices e.g., avoiding bias in data processing when using data-driven technologies applicable to their field of expertise. These include general ethical principles, frameworks and codes of conduct applicable to research e.g. the RRI Framework; the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity.
- Applying open publication practices, such as publishing preprints, publishing in open access journals and platforms, ensuring data and code are available in open repositories to the extent possible.
- Engaging with stakeholders outside academia to maximize research impact.

Soft / Transversal Skills - considered equally important by Skills4EOSC, these are not specific to the occupation or sector.

- Effective communication
- Ability to provide constructive feedback
- Research management and leadership
- Time and people management
- Teamwork and collaboration
- Problem-solving
- Research integrity

Background assumptions

Main activities

- Applies Open Science policies, strategies and best practices.
- Promotes and supports Open Science principles in their disciplinary fields by training other researchers in open science practices, methods and skills.
- Contributes to education and professional development of students and Early Career Researchers by developing curricula and programs in Open Science methods, including data management.
- Provides researchers in their group with appropriate knowledge and support to understand regulatory, ethical and policy requirements affecting their research.
- Designs and manages research activities.
- Builds and coordinates research teams.
- Establishes collaboration network.

Contributes to which Open Science outcomes?

The main objective of the Senior Researcher is to conduct and oversee high quality and reproducible research, undertaken with integrity. Given their role in supervision, education, hiring, journal editing, peer review, and informing institutional policies, Senior Researchers can establish a research environment that supports and implements Open Science. Crucially, Senior Researchers have a responsibility to manage and nurture Early Career Researchers. This can be achieved via the following:

- Applies Open Science policies, strategies and best practices.
- Promotes and supports Open Science principles in their disciplinary fields by training other researchers in open science practices, methods and skills.
- Contributes to education and professional development of students and Early Career Researchers by developing curricula and programs in Open Science methods, including data management.
- Provides researchers in their group with appropriate knowledge and support to understand regulatory, ethical and policy requirements affecting their research.

- Designs and manages research activities.
- Builds and coordinates research teams.
- Establishes collaboration network.

Further information

Contributors: Saba Sharma, Dominique Green, Irakleitos Souyioultzoglou, Gabriela Torres-Ramos, Claire Sowinski, Karolina Dostatnia, Luca Schirru, Angus Whyte

Open Science skills terms

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ESCO Research Skills: [Demonstrate disciplinary expertise](#); [Manage findable accessible interoperable and reusable data](#); [Manage research data](#); [Synthesise information](#); [Apply for research funding](#); [Mentor individuals](#); [Teach in academic or vocational contexts](#); [Promote the transfer of knowledge](#); [Communicate with a non-scientific audience](#); [Increase the impact of science on policy and society](#); [Manage intellectual property rights](#); [Manage open publications](#); [Apply research ethics and scientific integrity principles in research activities](#); [Promote the participation of citizens in scientific and research activities](#); [Perform project management](#); [Integrate gender dimension in research](#).

ESCO Transversal Skills: [Report facts](#); [Manage financial and material resources](#); [Show entrepreneurial spirit](#); [Advise others](#); [Address an audience](#); [Instruct others](#); [Build networks](#); [Organise information, objects and resources](#); [Respect confidentiality obligations](#); [Moderate a discussion](#); [Use communication and collaboration software](#); [Critically evaluate information and its sources](#); [Think critically](#); [Show empathy](#); [Lead others](#); [Adapt to change](#); [Meet commitments](#); [Plan](#); [Show initiative](#); [Assume responsibility](#); [Make decisions](#); [Manage time](#); [Resolve conflicts](#); [Negotiate compromises](#); [Show commitment](#); [Work in teams](#); [Build team spirit](#); [Demonstrate intercultural competence](#); [Show determination](#); [Solve problems](#); [Think analytically](#); [Demonstrate trustworthiness](#).

ResearchComp: Abstract thinking; Strategic thinking; Write research documents; Mobilise resources; Promote open innovation; Teach in academic or vocational contexts; Promote the transfer of knowledge; Communicate to the broad public; Increase the impact of science on policy and society; Negotiate; Promote open access publishing; Participate in publication process; Manage personal professional development; Promote citizen science; Critical thinking; Evaluate research; Plan self-organisation; Ensure wellbeing at work.

Terms4FAIRskills: [Assessment on FAIR data criteria](#); [Knowledge to contextualise fair principles to domain](#); [Mentoring on open and fair methods](#); [Training in open and fair methods](#); [Crediting research contributors](#); [Data analysis](#); [Data categorisation](#); [Data curation](#); [Data destruction](#); [Data discovery](#); [Data driven decision management](#); [Data harmonization](#); [Data sharing and publication](#); [Depositing in repository](#); [Evaluating repositories for data deposit/sharing](#); [Data access risk assessment and mitigation](#); [Ethical application of patents, licenses](#); [Data policy](#); [Open peer review](#); [Stakeholder engagement on societal impact](#); [Research management](#); [Research integrity](#).

[attribution, impact awareness](#); [Data sharing and publication](#).

CSCCE: [Strategy development](#); [Content creation and curation](#); [Content planning](#); [Record keeping](#); [Landscape analysis](#); [Speaking and presenting](#); [Proposal development](#); [Advancement, growth and sustainability](#); [Collaboration](#); [Data analysis](#); [Advancement, growth and sustainability](#); [Engagement](#); [Evaluation and assessment](#).

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Research Infrastructure Professional

V0.6 2025

DOCUMENT LOG

Issue	Date	Comment	Author
0.1	31/03/2023	Initial content	Karla Avanço, Arnaud Gingold, Päivi Rauste, Irakleitos Souyioultzoglou, Claire Sowinski, Gabriela Torres-Ramos
0.2	27/04/2023	Review	Marialuisa Lavitrano, Enrico Guarini, Sara Casati
0.3	04/05/2023	Review additions integrated ELSI aspects integrated	Karla Avanço, Arnaud Gingold, Päivi Rauste, Irakleitos Souyioultzoglou, Claire Sowinski, Gabriela Torres-Ramos
0.4	09/05/2023	Review by task leader	Karla Avanço, Arnaud Gingold, Angus Whyte
0.5	19/11/2024	Conversion to a new template	Elena Sokolova
0.6	17/06/2025	Alignment with survey texts Removed non-essential terms	Claire Sowinski, Angus Whyte

Introduction: Open Science mission for this role

Research Infrastructures (RIs) support “research communities to conduct research and foster innovation” and constitute a major component in building an OS environment in so far as they aim at both “skilling researchers” and providing a wide range of “supporting staff”. RIs pool together tools, Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) and good practices to monitor and make accessible the entire research process.

The Minimum Viable Skillset (MVS) for Research Infrastructure (RI) professionals therefore considers the specificities of the functions represented in such organizations with regard to Open Science (OS). The functions can be diverse and correspond to many function titles, however, as these functions are in great part defined by the organization’s role, the content, context, and prospect of the missions are common to all RI professionals. The MVS for RI professionals proposes therefore a generic description of the role, which can be applied with adjustments to various functions. More detailed descriptions of specific functions can be found in other MVS, e.g. in the MVS for data stewards operating in RIs.

The OS missions of RI professionals therefore entail: spreading a Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) and OS culture; managing the RI; providing, handling and maintaining services, resources, and tools; harmonizing and improving a common EU OS space; supporting and monitoring FAIRification; providing training, sharing best practices, and building a research community.

Research Infrastructures professionals

Research Infrastructure (RI) professionals contribute to open science development by being “operators who have experience and insights into scientific or technical issues whilst also being a professional manager”. RI professionals also play a specific role in coordinating and engaging the scientific community.

Associated function titles: Infrastructure manager, Project manager, Service manager, Chief Technology Officer, Data manager, Data steward, Researcher.

Essential Skills for this Role

- Expertise and competence in Responsible Research & Innovation, OS and research governance, based on knowledge of diverse EU research policies and systems.
- Technical knowledge and skills needed for service development and provision, including data use agreements, information security and risk management.
- Staff management and project management.
- Ability to plan and implement FAIR and open science principles and reproducible research by empowering people to implement transparent, accountable and sustainable processes that meet scientific communities’ identified needs.
- Expertise in developing guidelines in multidisciplinary areas.
- Fostering a common vision among various stakeholders.
- Ability to understand ethical and legal implications of research, including:
 - Intellectual property rights and non-personal data management.
 - Knowledge of Ethical principles, frameworks and codes of conduct.
 - Legal issues related to personal data governance.
 - Responsible use of data-driven technologies.
- Ability to create, plan, coordinate public events and information pathways.

Soft/ transversal skills - considered equally important by Skills4EOSC, these are not specific to the occupation or sector.

- Networking in inclusive/pluralist/participatory environments.
- Community engagement expertise.
- Team building and teamwork.
- Leadership and coordination.
- Sharing knowledge and processes.
- Pedagogical skills.

- Analytical and research skills
- Flexibility and adaptability
- Proactiveness and responsiveness

Background assumptions

Main activities

Service

- Provide knowledge-related facilities and resources such as collections, archives or scientific data infrastructures; computing systems, communication networks, and any other infrastructure.
- Provide technological alignment, standards implementation.
- Provide guidance about FAIR principles and FAIR implementation.
- Ensure technical policy consistency throughout projects and activities of the RI.

Support

- Coordinate and engage the research community's relevant stakeholders with a special attention to young generation.
- Set up and offer foundational and specialized digital skills training for scientific community, data professionals, ELSI experts, Data Protection Officers.
- Facilitate in-person and online training and development of communities of practice.
- Support the application of RRI principles through the anticipation of impact and the consideration of inclusiveness and transparency dimensions of research.
- Instruct researchers on open licensing and open software according to the legislation on the reuse of public funded research data.

Coordination

- Foster new partnerships and innovative services through internal and external collaboration.
- Share knowledge to address socio-economic challenges and take care of users' needs.
- Position the RI in the local, national and international environment; identify regional research priorities and set consistent strategies.
- Identify and negotiate with potential funders; identify new funding tools e.g. private-public partnerships, special projects, commercial funding, fee for service, consultancy.

Contributes to which Open Science outcomes?

The European Commission describes the main objectives of RIs and these represent OS outcomes provided by the RI professionals:

- OS practices are generalised, and fragmentation of the research ecosystem is reduced.
- Duplication of effort is avoided.

- Research outputs sharing is facilitated and supported.
- Open, usable and accessible research data and publications are produced.
- Innovation and research projects are boosted.
- Cross-disciplinarity and cooperation with industry is facilitated.

Further information

Contributors: Karla Avanço, Arnaud Gingold, Irakleitos Souyioultzoglou, Elena Sokolova, Angus Whyte

Open Science skills terms

OS skills terms match the essential skills in this MVS to competence definitions from relevant taxonomies. The selected terms offer further information to help identify the learning objectives for skills development. Sources: European Skills, Competences and Occupations ontology ([ESCO](#)), [ResearchComp](#), [terms4FAIRskills](#), [Center Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement](#).

ESCO Research Skills: [Communicate with a non-scientific audience](#); [Conduct research across disciplines](#); [Develop professional network with researchers and scientists](#); [Draft scientific or academic papers and technical documentation](#); [Increase the impact of science on policy and society](#); [Interact professionally in research and professional environments](#); [Manage findable accessible interoperable and reusable data](#); [Manage intellectual property rights](#); [Manage open publications](#); [Manage personal professional development](#); [Manage research data](#); [Negotiate compromises](#); [Operate open source software](#); [Perform project management](#); [Promote open innovation in research](#); [Promote the transfer of knowledge](#).

ESCO Transversal Skills: [Adapt to change](#); [Address an audience](#); [Advise others](#); [Assume responsibility](#); [Build networks](#); [Demonstrate curiosity](#); [Demonstrate intercultural competence](#); [Manage financial and material resources](#); [Manage time](#); [Moderate a discussion](#); [Motivate others](#); [Organise information, objects and resources](#); [Plan](#); [Promote ideas, products, services](#); [Resolve conflicts](#); [Respect the diversity of cultural values and norms](#); [Show commitment](#); [Show confidence](#); [Show initiative](#); [Think analytically](#); [Think holistically](#); [Think innovatively](#); [Think quickly](#); [Use communication and collaboration software](#); [Work in teams](#).

ResearchComp: Apply research ethics and integrity principles; Ensure well-being at work; Interact professionally; Manage intellectual property rights; Mobilise resources.

Terms4FAIRskills: [Data access risk assessment and mitigation](#); [Data costs management](#); [Data governance](#); [Data policy](#); [Knowledge to contextualise fair principles to domain](#); [Meeting/conference organisation](#); [Research integrity, attribution, impact awareness](#); [Selecting appropriate data handling methods](#); [Strategic/long-term planning](#); [Training in open and fair methods](#).

CSCCE: [Advancement, growth and sustainability](#); [Advocacy](#); [Business modeling](#); [Change management](#); [Collaboration](#); [Community governance](#); [Knowledge brokering](#); [Landscape analysis](#); [Meeting facilitation](#); [Moderation, mediation and intervention](#); [Networking](#); [Operational planning and implementation](#); [Outreach](#); [Proposal development](#); [Strategy development](#).

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Scholarly Communications Professional

V0.5 2025

DOCUMENT LOG

Issue	Date	Comment	Author
0.1	10/06/2023	Initial content	Karla Avanço, Arnaud Gingold, Irakleitos Souyioultzoglou
0.2	28/06/2023	Reviewed content	Karla Avanço, Arnaud Gingold, Irakleitos Souyioultzoglou
0.3	10/07/2023	Review	Angus Whyte
0.4	19/11/2024	Conversion to a new template	Elena Sokolova
0.5	30/04/2025	Removed non-essential terms	Claire Sowinski, Angus Whyte

Introduction: Open Science mission for this role

According to UNESCO, “Scholarly communication is the process of sharing, disseminating and publishing research findings of academics and researchers so that the generated academic contents are made available to the global academic communities”³. The Minimum Viable Skillset for Scholarly Communication Professionals describes the Open Science and Data Management skills required for those roles contributing to the creation, curation, and dissemination of scholarly outputs, with a particular attention to publications. Publications and scholarly outputs in general are not only the result of scientific activities, but a component of the open science ecosystem and therefore requiring the same OS and RDM skills as other OS products.

Scholarly Communication Professional

The Scholarly Communication Professional (SCP) deals with Scholarly Communication Artifacts, which entail, but are not limited to: articles, books, posts, annotations. SCPs engaged in Open Science ensure open access to the Scholarly Communication Artifacts, and more broadly their full integration into the OS environment. SCPs not only apply OS and RDM principles to the traditional and innovative forms of Scholarly Communication Artifacts, but they also address OS aspects beyond RDM best practices.

In that prospect, the SCP designs and/or implements OS policies and recommendations and applies methods and standards to ensure high-quality, accessible and reproducible research outputs.

Associated function titles: Publisher, Editor, Librarian.

Organisational context: Libraries, Research Performing Organizations (learned societies, universities, research centres), Scientific publishers, Research Infrastructures.

Essential Skills for this Role

³ <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000231938>.

- Expertise in data literacy both as a practitioner and a trainer.
- Knowledge of repositories and aggregator types, scope, and requirements.
- Knowledge of open publication models (green, gold, diamond).
- Ability to generate and understand bibliometrics, altmetrics, and usage metrics.
- Ability to apply FAIR principles to a variety of scholarly outputs, including expertise in persistent identification of contents, standard metadata generation and storage, and good knowledge of discipline-specific output types and standards.
- Knowledge about Linked Open Data and semantic interoperability.
- Knowledge about legal aspects related to IP/copyright/privacy, as well as data protection for sensitive data and information. Includes the ability to balance data protection requirements with open science/FAIR principles.
- Knowledge and ability to apply Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) and the CARE (Collective benefit, Authority to control, Responsibility, Ethics) principles.
- Ability to design, organize, and manage physical and digital trainings and events.

Soft/ transversal skills - considered equally important by Skills4EOSC, these are not specific to the occupation or sector.

- Team management and project management, for results-oriented planning and organisation.
- Stakeholder engagement and networking to translate and bridge needs.
- Creativity, curiosity and openness with a willingness to learn.
- Critical and analytical thinking.
- Conflict management and mediation, with a patient, empathic approach.

Background assumptions

Main activities

- Maintains and/or uses a publishing platform or a repository providing interoperable contents.
- Guides and supports users in disseminating standardized and FAIRified scholarly communication artifacts.
- Guides and supports users in enhancing their data literacy skills and working effectively with various types of data.
- Negotiates with publishers for open access publishing.
- Curates and enriches the data to ensure semantic and technical interoperability with a range of aggregators' specifications.
- Uses tools and follows procedures to achieve sustainability of published resources.
- Ensures compliance of published output with ethical and legal recommendations.
- Organises and monitors processes of content creation, review and dissemination.

- Integrates the aspects of diversity, inclusiveness and integrity in the process of information sharing.
- Participates and contributes to trans-professional networks including librarians, publishers, IT experts, legal experts, etc.

Contributes to which Open Science outcomes?

The SCP manages Scholarly Communication Artifacts as research data, following OS and RDM principles, including the FAIR principles, both for the contents (e.g. using interoperable standard structured formats), and for their metadata (e.g., using PIDs and standard metadata schemas). The SCP ensures this way that Scholarly Communication Artifacts are not only disseminated as research results but made available as reusable research data.

LIBER (Association of European Research Libraries) identifies the following contributions to OS proper to librarians that also characterize any SCP's activity:

- Scholarly Communication Artifacts are accessible as research data, with relevant metrics, following OS and RDM principles.

Research integrity is enhanced by applying FAIR principles both to artifact contents e.g. using interoperable standard structured formats, and to their metadata e.g. using PIDs and standard metadata schemas.

Further information

Contributors: Karla Avanço, Arnaud Gingold, Irakleitos Souyioultzoglou, Elena Sokolova, Angus Whyte

Open Science skills terms

OS skills terms match the essential skills in this MVS to competence definitions from relevant taxonomies. The selected terms offer further information to help identify the learning objectives for skills development. Sources: European Skills, Competences and Occupations ontology ([ESCO](#)), [ResearchComp](#), [terms4FAIRskills](#), [Center Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement](#).

ESCO Research Skills: [Apply research ethics and scientific integrity principles in research activities](#); [Develop professional network with researchers and scientists](#); [Interact professionally in research and professional environments](#); [Manage findable accessible interoperable and reusable data](#); [Manage open publications](#); [Manage research data](#); [Operate open-source software](#); [Perform project management](#); [Promote the transfer of knowledge](#); [Teach in academic or vocational contexts](#); [Think abstractly](#).

ESCO Transversal Skills: [Advise others](#); [Apply basic programming skills](#); [Apply digital security measures](#); [Apply knowledge of science, technology and engineering](#); [Build networks](#); [Comply with regulations](#); [Demonstrate willingness to learn](#); [Instruct others](#); [Manage quality](#); [Manage time](#); [Organize information, objects and resources](#); [Plan](#); [Promote ideas, products, services](#); [Resolve conflicts](#); [Respect the diversity of cultural values and norms](#); [Show empathy](#); [Show initiative](#); [Solve problems](#); [Think analytically](#); [Think creatively](#); [Think critically](#); [Use communication and collaboration software](#); [Work in teams](#).

ResearchComp: Abstract thinking; Interact professionally; Mobilise resources; Negotiate; Promote the transfer of knowledge.

Terms4FAIRskills: [Assessment on FAIR data criteria](#); [Community building](#); [Data access risk assessment and mitigation](#); [Data archiving](#); [Data categorisation](#); [Data curation](#); [Data governance](#); [Data policy](#); [Data quality assessment & review](#); [Digital archiving](#); [Evaluating repositories for data deposit/sharing](#); [Information security](#); [Knowledge to contextualize FAIR principles to domain](#); [Meeting/conference organization](#); [Mentoring on open and FAIR methods](#); [Metadata creation](#); [Metadata exposure](#); [Preservation](#); [Privacy governance](#); [Training in open and FAIR methods](#); [User acceptance testing](#).

CSCCE: [Advocacy](#); [Collaboration](#); [Community governance](#); [Consultation and listening](#); [Cultural competence](#); [Engagement](#); [Event planning](#); [Knowledge brokering](#); [Landscape analysis](#); [Media production](#); [Meeting facilitation](#); [Moderation, mediation and intervention](#); [Networking](#); [Operational planning and implementation](#); [Outreach](#); [Record-keeping](#); [Speaking and presenting](#); [Teaching and training](#).

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Student – Masters Level

V0.5 2025

DOCUMENT LOG

Issue	Date	Comment	Author
0.1		Initial content	Dominique Green, Saba Sharma, Irakleitos Souyioultzoglou, Gabriela Torres-Ramos, Claire Sowinski, Karolina Dostatnia
0.2		Draft for internal review	As above and Benjamin Derksen, Lorna Wildgaard, Bernd Saurugger, Paula Martinez Lavanchy, Carolin Leister, Luca Schirru
0.3	10/10/2024	Revised to update the MVS layout	Dominique Green
0.4	12/12/2024	Revised to add Open Science Skills terms	Dominique Green
0.5	17/06/2025	Removed non-essential terms	Claire Sowinski, Angus Whyte

Introduction: Open Science mission for this role

The Minimum Viable Skillset (MVS) for Master's students is one of two MVS for students (the other for undergraduate students). As Master's level education is more specialised and focused than the undergraduate level this MVS considers the skills and competencies in Open Science (OS) needed for more focused study, incorporating OS into their project workflows. This is a generic profile for students in postgraduate education.

For information related to basic skills for researchers, see the MVS designed specifically for early career researchers, which addresses the minimum skills and competencies needed for PhD student and post-doctoral researchers.

It is recognised that Open Science skills should be immersed within formal education at its earliest stages. By engaging with Open Science practices and acquiring relevant knowledge of OS early in their careers, the benefits of these practices can be recognised, even if their careers are not in academia.

Master's student

Organisational context:

- Research Performing Organizations

Essential Skills for this Role

- Ability to analyse OS and FAIR concepts and ideas in the respective field of study. Where relevant, includes knowledge of ways to share and produce FAIR research data, code and

software, and of how to use data repositories.

- Intermediate digital research skills, data management, data communication. Includes demonstrating an understanding of the research life cycle, including planning, design, analysis, publication, and dissemination. Includes the ability to organise project workflow using file folders, document naming conventions, version control, cloud storage (etc.).
- Ability to obtain open science knowledge and apply FAIR principles, including relevant discipline or domain-specific information. Includes performing literature and data searches efficiently: finding and reusing open scientific papers, as well as finding, understanding, (re)using, and analysing the appropriate data types and formats for assignments.
- Open publication literacy skills, including knowledge of how to navigate open access sources and open access publication models applied to OA repositories.
- Basic understanding of the relevant legal issues related to Open Science practices, including Intellectual Property Rights, copyright-related issues like Open Access, Open Licensing, using and citing third-parties works. Also includes Non-Personal Data e.g., being aware of rules on the use of "research data".
- Knowledge of how to apply data protection requirements together with Open Science/FAIR principles. Includes Personal Data Protection and Governance e.g., using Personal Data under the current legal framework, and following Data Protection policies.
- General understanding of ethical principles e.g. transparency, diversity and accountability; and best practices e.g. avoiding bias in data processing when using data-driven technologies. Includes ability to relate these principles to their field of expertise, by applying the general ethical principles, frameworks and codes of conduct, e.g. the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity.

Soft/ transversal skills - considered equally important by Skills4EOSC, these are not specific to the occupation or sector.

- Collaboration skills, ability to engage in teamwork.
- Assignment and/or dissertation management.
- Organizational skills, including goal setting, time management, and prioritizing.
- Verbal communication and interpersonal skills.
- Written communication.
- Problem solving.
- Critical thinking.
- Presentation skills.

Background assumptions

Main activities

- Engages with OS outputs, and contributes to data literacy activities that improve their understanding of the concepts and principles of Open Science, including:
- Interpreting and critically evaluating data.
- Finding, selecting, accessing, and creating data sets.
- Ethically using and citing data.
- Understanding basic data types and formats.
- Communicating data with visualizations.
- Understanding how data is collected.
- Manipulating data from different sources, formats, and structures.
- Understanding how to store and share data.
- Understanding why it is important to manage data.
- Plans, organises, and manages assignments related to dissertations. Specific activities related to OS include:
- Using a data management plan to describe efforts to make research reproducible, including providing descriptions of the data via metadata, research procedures and analyses.
- Writing manuscripts and/or dissertations transparently, sharing hypotheses and justifying decisions, and sharing methodologies.
- Sharing any data used for projects, making the data available for researchers.

Contributes to which Open Science outcomes?

Non-research graduate students contribute to the following Open Science outcomes:

- The adoption and practice of OS and FAIR principles and methods.
- Increasing transparency and knowledge sharing in research processes.
- Increasing knowledge and awareness of digital literacy.

Further information

Contributors: Dominique Green, Saba Sharma, Irakleitos Souyioultzoglou, Gabriela Torres-Ramos, Claire Sowinski, Karolina Dostatnia, Luca Schirru, Angus Whyte, Paula Martinez Lavanchy, Carolin Leister, Bernd Sarugger.

Open Science skills terms

OS skills terms match the essential skills in this MVS to competence definitions from relevant taxonomies. Terms are selected to add further information and to aid discovery of this MVS (an extended list is added at the foot of this document). Sources: European Skills, Competences and Occupations ontology ([ESCO](#)), [ResearchComp](#), [terms4FAIRskills](#), [Center Scientific Collaboration](#)

[and Community Engagement.](#)

ESCO Research Skills: [Perform project management](#); [Manage research data](#); [Synthesize research publications](#); [Manage open publications](#); [Manage findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable data](#); [Operate open source software](#); [Manage intellectual property rights](#); [Apply research ethics and scientific integrity principles in research activities.](#)

ESCO Transversal Skills: [Plan, conduct web searches](#); [apply knowledge of science, technology, and engineering](#); [Work in teams](#); [address an audience](#); [Moderate a discussion](#); [Report facts](#); [Use communication and collaboration software](#); [Manage time](#); [Organise information, objects, and resources](#); [Solve problems](#); [Critically evaluate information and its sources](#); [Think critically](#); [Show initiative](#); [Assume responsibility](#); [Show confidence.](#)

ResearchComp: Manage research data; Apply research ethics and integrity principles; Problem solving; Creativity.

Terms4FAIRskills: [Data transformation](#); [Data validation and cleaning](#); [Open access publishing](#); [Data access risk assessment and mitigation](#); [Ethical application of patents, licenses](#); [Research governance](#); [Data policy.](#)

CSCCE: [Data analysis](#); [Data visualization](#); [Speaking and presenting](#); [Time management.](#)

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Student – Undergraduate level

V0.6 2025

DOCUMENT LOG

Issue	Date	Comment	Author
0.1		Initial content	Gabriela Torres-Ramos, Dominique Green, Saba Sharma, Irakleitos Souyioultzoglou, , Claire Sowinski, Karolina Dostatnia
0.2		Draft for discussion	As above + comments from Paula Martinez, Lorna Wildgaard, Carolin Leister, Benjamin Derksen, Bernd Saurugger
0.3		Draft v3 for internal review	As above
0.4	11/10/2024	Updated MVS layout	Dominique Green
0.5	12/12/2024	Updated profile to include Open Science skills terms	Dominique Green
0.6	17/06/2025	Alignment with survey texts Removed non-essential terms	Claire Sowinski, Angus Whyte

Introduction: Open Science mission for this role

It is recognized that Open Science skills should be immersed within formal education at its earliest stages. Undergraduates are potential future researchers and open science practitioners. By taking part in relevant open science training early, undergraduates become concerned citizens and better equipped to support open science.

The Minimum Viable Skillset (MVS) for Undergraduates addresses the minimum competencies and skills needed by undergraduate students at the completion of their degree program in Open Science (OS). The MVS profile for undergraduates considers that undergraduate students do not typically undertake extensive research projects. However, there are opportunities for undergraduates to interact with data and software whilst working on assignments. Therefore, this MVS for undergraduate students is a general profile developed specifically in regard to data literacy knowledge, as it serves as basis for relevant OS activities and knowledge of the FAIR principles. For information related to basic skills for graduate students who are undertaking research activities, typically via dissertations and other assignments, see the MVS designed for Master's Students. For the basic skills and competencies needed for early career researchers, including postgraduate students (PhDs), please see the MVS for early career researchers.

Undergraduate students

Organisational context:

- Research Performing Organisations (Universities)

Essential Skills for this Role

- Understanding of why it is important for society that research and data is open and FAIR.
- Ability to identify open science and FAIR principles, including relevant discipline or domain-specific information.
- Foundational digital research skills, e.g. knowledge of the research life cycle; organizing and documenting.
- Understand basic concepts of intellectual property and copyright and its importance in scientific work.
- Ability to identify the principles of open licensing and the uses and implications of open licenses.
- Know what is meant by research impact. Know the different types of impact indicators and how they work.
- Understand the importance of research visibility and know different ways to increase the visibility of research.
- Ability to apply basic open science principles in the relevant parts of the research life cycle, such as:
 - Recognising reliable and trustworthy sources of data.
 - Evaluating the quality and reusability of data.
 - Recognising the different open access model for scientific publications.
 - Knowledge of how to share FAIR research data, code and software, including knowledge of how to use repositories.

Soft / Transversal Skills - considered equally important by Skills4EOSC, these are not specific to the occupation or sector.

- Collaboration and interpersonal skills, being particularly able to engage in teamwork.
- Written and verbal communication
- Time management
- Problem solving
- Critical thinking

Background assumptions

Main activities

- Contributes to data literacy activities that improves their OS knowledge and skills, including:
 - Interpreting and critically evaluating data.
 - Finding, selecting, accessing, and creating data sets.
 - Ethically using, collecting and citing data.

- Understanding basic data types and formats.
- Communicating data with appropriate visualizations.
- Understanding how the data was collected.

Contributes to which Open Science outcomes?

The undergraduate contributes to the following OS outcomes:

- Development of data literacy abilities.
- Acquisition of a baseline of generic foundational digital skills.
- Adoption, awareness and understanding of OS and FAIR principles.
- Adoption of responsible and ethical use of data.

Further information

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Open Science skills terms

OS skills terms match the essential skills in this MVS to competence definitions from relevant taxonomies. Terms are selected to add further information and to aid discovery of this MVS (an extended list is added at the foot of this document). Sources: European Skills, Competences and Occupations ontology ([ESCO](#)), [ResearchComp](#), [terms4FAIRskills](#), [Center Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement](#).

ESCO Research Skills: [Synthesise research publications](#); [Manage open publications](#); [Apply research ethics and scientific integrity principles in research activities](#); [Manage findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable data](#).

ESCO Transversal Skills: [Plan, Organise information, objects, and resources](#); [Conduct web searches](#); [Show commitment](#); [Work in teams](#); [Build team spirit](#); [Address an audience](#); [Report facts](#); [Use communication and collaboration software](#); [Moderate a discussion](#); [Manage time](#); [Critically evaluate information and its sources](#); [Apply knowledge of science, technology and engineering](#).

ResearchComp: Problem solving; Creativity.

Terms4FAIRskills: [Assessment on FAIR data criteria](#); [Data sharing and publication](#); [Data quality assessment](#); [Open access publishing](#).

CSCCE: [Speaking and presenting](#).

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